

The New and Axiom-Less Foundation of All Human Knowledge: Manuscript 12

The New Theory of Existence: Part 2 Philosophical theory of everything

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Abstract

This manuscript is a part of a series of manuscripts named 'The New and Axiom-Less Foundation of All Human Knowledge'. This manuscript is a part of the sub-series of this series, called as 'Existence sub-series'.

After the completion of exploration of the real underlying mechanism of existence as well as the eternity beyond the illusion of material world, in previous manuscript of 'Existence sub-series', in this manuscript we will explore the philosophical theory of everything, based on the bottom-up approach of knowledge exploration.

This manuscript dissolved the boundary between the 2 currently completely distinct domains of science & philosophy.

Keywords

Phenomenon of ego | Phenomenon of desire | Phenomenon of pleasure |
Phenomenon of 'Knowledge, clarity & vision' | Phenomenon of choice |
Dissolving of boundary between science & philosophy

List of series-manuscripts

Manuscript 1

The New Foundation for All Human Knowledge: Manuscript 1
An introduction to the Series of manuscripts

Knowledge sub-series

Part 1 | Manuscript 2

The New and Axiom-Less Foundation of All Human Knowledge: Manuscript 2
The New Foundation of Knowledge Exploration: Part 1

Phenomenon of knowledge | Claim of knowledge
Shortform to address this manuscript in content :: Knowledge 1

Part 2 | Manuscript 3

The New and Axiom-Less Foundation of All Human Knowledge: Manuscript 3
The New Foundation of Knowledge Exploration: Part 2

Journey towards knowledge | Core of indirect knowing | Mystery of knowing
Shortform to address this manuscript in content :: Knowledge 2

Part 3 | Manuscript 4

The New and Axiom-Less Foundation of All Human Knowledge: Manuscript 4
The New Foundation of Knowledge Exploration: Part 3

Knowledge exploration process | Phenomenon of inherent similarity
Shortform to address this manuscript in content :: Knowledge 3

Part 4 | Manuscript 5

The New and Axiom-Less Foundation of All Human Knowledge: Manuscript 5

The New Foundation of Knowledge Exploration: Part 4

Aid for knowledge exploration process

Shortform to address this manuscript in content :: Knowledge 4

Part 5 | Manuscript 6

The New and Axiom-Less Foundation of All Human Knowledge: Manuscript 6

The New Foundation of Knowledge Exploration: Part 5

Aid for knowledge exploration process wrt perception phenomenon

Shortform to address this manuscript in content :: Knowledge 5

Part 6 | Manuscript 7

The New and Axiom-Less Foundation of All Human Knowledge: Manuscript 7

The New Foundation of Knowledge Exploration: Part 6

Unanswered questions & unsolved paradoxes related to phenomenon of
knowledge & knowledge exploration

Shortform to address this manuscript in content :: Knowledge 6

Mathematics sub-series

Part 1 | Manuscript 8

The New and Axiom-Less Foundation of All Human Knowledge: Manuscript 8

The New Foundation of Mathematics: Part 1

Core of phenomenon of mathematics | New mathematics system

Shortform to address this manuscript in content :: Mathematics 1

Part 2 | Manuscript 9

The New and Axiom-Less Foundation of All Human Knowledge: Manuscript 9

The New Foundation of Mathematics: Part 2

Flaws related to current mathematics system

Shortform to address this manuscript in content :: Mathematics 2

Part 3 | Manuscript 10

The New and Axiom-Less Foundation of All Human Knowledge: Manuscript 10

The New Foundation of Mathematics: Part 3

Unanswered questions & unsolved paradoxes & flaws in theorems related to mathematics

Shortform to address this manuscript in content :: Mathematics 3

Existence sub-series

Part 1 | Manuscript 11

The New and Axiom-Less Foundation of All Human Knowledge: Manuscript 11

The New Theory of Existence: Part 1

Reaching the real underlying mechanism of existence | This is eternity

Shortform to address this manuscript in content :: Existence 1

Part 2 | Manuscript 12

The New and Axiom-Less Foundation of All Human Knowledge: Manuscript 12

The New Theory of Existence: Part 2

Philosophical theory of everything

Shortform to address this manuscript in content :: Existence 2

Part 3 | Manuscript 13

The New and Axiom-Less Foundation of All Human Knowledge: Manuscript 13

The New Theory of Existence: Part 3

Theory of everything

Shortform to address this manuscript in content :: Existence 3

1 | Part A

Phenomenon of desire | Phenomenon of pleasure

1.1 | Phenomenon of philosophy related

1.1.1 | Phenomenon of choice | Positivity & negativity

1.1.1.a | Importance of choice related

If there is one thing which is responsible to make or break our life, and that one thing is 'choice'. The most core aspect of our life as, of our existence, is 'choice'.

Whatever your life is right now, is a byproduct of the choices you made. And the direction in which your life would head, would also be a byproduct of the choices you would make. Every single choice that we make, knowingly or unknowingly, has an effect on our future.

To gain something, you have to lose something. You cannot gain something if you do not want to lose anything, as gain and loss, co-exists.

But what is it that you gain, and what is it that you lose, that is the important question. What you gain and what you lose, depends on what you choose.

Whatever state the world is now, at the core of it is phenomenon of choice. Whether this would be a pleasurable place or a miserable place, the core responsible for this is the phenomenon of choice.

Phenomenon of knowledge has importance because it aids in our choices. So phenomenon of choice has critical importance, as well as it is critically important to understand the phenomenon of choice.

1.1.1.b | Choice is inevitable | Not making choice, is an illusionary idea | Ultimate non-absolute form related

Choice is inevitable

If there is one thing about our material existence, then it is that, choice is inevitable. You cannot escape choice, it is impossible.

At every point in your life, at every moment in your life, you are making choice. This choice may be conscious or subconscious, knowingly or unknowingly, but you are making choice. You always have, you always will, at every instance, make choice.

At every point in your life, at every moment in your life, you do have choice. The perception that you have of how the things are and how the things should be; and based on that would follow those things. This following is the choice you are make.

This perception of blindly following, keeps you ignorant from the realization of the existence of choice.

Not making choice, is an illusionary idea

So here is a thing. Not making a choice, is also a choice. It is accepting whatever possibility that manifests, as your choice. So even if you don't choose, you are choosing not to choose.

At any point in your life, you thinking that you are not making choice, or it is possible to not make a choice, then that is an illusion you would be having. Not making a choice is an illusionary idea.

Ultimate non-absolute form related

As we have explored in previous manuscript 'Knowledge 4', non-absolute form is a phenomenon related to choice. And material world is a part of the ultimate non-absolute form, i.e. non-absolute form of the ultimate form.

So at the core of material world, is the phenomenon of choice. Existence of material world is based on the phenomenon of choice.

1.1.1.c | Nature of choice related

Types of nature of choice

Choice can be divided into 3 categories. Following are those 3 choices

1. Positive choice
 - If the choice has a positive or beneficial effect on our future, then that choice is a positive choice

2. Negative choice

- If the choice has a negative or adverse effect on our future, then that choice is a negative choice

3. Neutral choice

- If the choice has no negative or positive effect on our future, then that choice is a neutral choice

These are 3 types of nature of choice.

Overview of determining the nature of a choice

Now the question is, we talk about choice being positive and negative, but what is the base factor which is being affected, which is determining the nature of choice ?

That factor is 'the conditions'.

Nothing can be positive or negative, on its own; nothing can be beneficial or adverse, on its own; nothing can be better or worse on its own. All that exists through the existence of comparison.

Comparison of what ? Comparison of the conditions.

Conditions are not good or bad, better or worse on their own, but in comparison.

As we have explored in previous manuscripts of 'Knowledge sub-series', comparison is the core of our experience of material world.

The phenomenon remains the same in the case of phenomenon of choice.

And now the question is, exactly which conditions do we compare ?

We compare the current condition with the future condition. With which we do find the choices which are positive and the choices which are negative, and also the choices that are neutral.

Then to find the best choice amongst the positive choices that we found, we compare the positive choices with each other.

Then to find the ultimate best choice, i.e. the ultimate positive choice, we consider the time frames, i.e. vision.

Wrt current conditions

To determine the nature of choices, first, we compare the current condition with the future condition. With which we do find the choices which are

positive and the choices which are negative, and also the choices that are neutral.

If the choice that you make, is going to have positive effect i.e. beneficial effect, on future, i.e. if it is going to make future conditions better than the current conditions, then that choice is a positive choice.

If the choice that you make, is going to have negative effect, i.e. adverse effect, on future, i.e. if it is going to make future conditions worse than the current conditions, then that choice is a negative choice.

If the choice that you make, is neither going to have positive neither negative effect on future, i.e. it is going to make future conditions neither better nor worse than the current conditions, then that choice is neutral.

Wrt each other

Now the question is, what if all the choices are negative, or all the choices are positive, or mix of both ?

Conditions are not good or bad, better or worse on there own, but in comparison.

Choices are not positive or negative on there own, but in comparison.

Lesser positive choice is a negative choice wrt greater positive choice.

Suppose that you have 2 choices, choice A & choice B. And both the choices are positive wrt other choices.

But suppose that choice A has more positive effect on the future conditions than the choice B. So in that case, choice B, though it being a positive choice, it is a negative choice when compared to choice A.

Lesser negative choice is a positive choice wrt greater negative choice.

Suppose that you have only 2 choices, choice X & choice Y. And both the choices have negative effect on the future condition, so let us suppose them as negative choices.

But suppose that choice X has lesser negative effect on the future conditions than the choice Y. So in that case, choice X, though it being a negative choice, it is a positive choice when compared to choice Y. This the so-called 'choosing your poison'.

Wrt time frame

But now here is the most important & critical factor in determining the nature of choice. And that factor is the factor of 'time-frame'.

The main reference to figure out if the choice is positive, negative or neutral, is the time-frame. Time-frame is the base reference, all other references comes after this.

While figuring out if the choice is positive, negative or neutral, it is extremely critical to consider the factor of the time-frame.

While categorizing the choice as positive, negative and neutral, we do it based on comparison with the future conditioning. But which future conditioning are we talking about here; near future or future which is far away ?

Here we are talking wrt time frame.

A choice being negative, positive and neutral, that can vary depending upon the time frame that you consider.

Whatever time frame that you are functioning on, beyond that time frame, what effect does the choice that you make, have, on the future beyond that time frame, decides if that choice is negative, positive or neutral. So here we are considering the time frame which is larger than the current time frame that used to determine the nature of choice.

As the time frame changes, it is very possible that the nature of the same choice will change.

A choice which is negative wrt the smaller time frame might be positive wrt the larger time frame; and vice versa.

A choice which is positive wrt a smaller time frame, which turns out to be negative wrt the larger time frame, is ultimately a choice which is negative.

A choice which is negative on a smaller time frame, which turns out to be positive on a larger time frame, is ultimately a choice which is positive.

1.1.1.d | Positivity & negativity

Positivity & negativity are a phenomenon related to choice.

Positivity & negativity is determined based on the nature of choice(s) being made. Making choices that are positive, is positivity. Making choices that are negative, is negativity.

Whatever applies in determining a choice being positive or negative, also applies in determining positivity & negativity.

Positive & negative environment

The environment which exists based on the positive choices made, is a positive environment, i.e. environment with positivity. And the environment which exists based on the negative choices made, is a negative environment, i.e. environment with negativity.

1.1.2 | Phenomenon of 'knowledge, clarity & vision'

1.1.2.a | Choice-context

Here is a thing about choice. Choice is a contextual phenomenon. Choice being positive & negative is wrt the relevant context.

Choice has context to it. We can call it as choice-context.

As we just explored, to determine the nature of choice, we need to determine the condition(s) as being better & worse.

We first need to have depth of understanding as which conditions really are better & worse. Wrt the understanding of the conditions, our perception of truth should be in alignment with the truth.

This understanding is specific to the relevant person making the choice. In other words, the conditions being better or worse is specific to the relevant person making the choice.

Choice is a phenomenon specific to a certain person.

So the choice-context has 2 factors related to it. Following are those factors

- 1 The relevant conditions
 - a The relevant current conditions
 - b The possible choices [possible future conditions]
- 2 The relevant person

1.1.2.b | What is clarity ? | Clarity vs knowledge | Clarity wrt choice

What is clarity ?

Clarity of a certain phenomenon is about depth of understanding related to that certain phenomenon. Clarity is a stage in development of knowledge related to a certain phenomenon.

In development of knowledge, we go from part-perception [perception of a certain phenomenon] to complete perception [perception of existence]. Absolute clarity is fitting the part-perception, into the complete perception.

Absolute clarity of a certain phenomenon is knowledge of that phenomenon. Absolute clarity needs bottom-up approach of knowledge.

Note [wrt this series]

Note a point here that, unless & until 'non-absolute clarity' is mentioned in this series of manuscripts, the term 'clarity' would mean 'absolute clarity'.

Clarity vs knowledge

Absolute clarity is the knowledge itself of the phenomenon. With the term clarity' [absolute clarity], we are addressing the knowledge of phenomenon, in isolation. And with the term 'knowledge' wrt a phenomenon, we are addressing the knowledge of phenomenon wrt the complete picture. So we can say that, knowledge is the base of clarity.

Clarity wrt choice

In case of choice, we are addressing specific conditions wrt the relevant person. In other words, we are addressing a certain variation of the scenario. And even if we might have the knowledge, we need to develop the clarity related to that specific scenario, i.e. the choice-context. So it is appropriate to call it as clarity, rather than knowledge, even after development of absolute clarity related to the choice-context.

Here to develop clarity related to choice-context, you need to have knowledge. So in the case of choice, it is not development of knowledge [complete perception] through development of clarity [part-perception]. This is about development of clarity [absolute clarity of part-perception] based on knowledge [complete perception].

This is another reason for it being appropriate to call the knowing related to choice-context, as clarity, rather than calling it as knowledge.

1.1.2.c | What is vision ?

As we have explored just earlier in this manuscript, choice is a contextual phenomenon.

Time-frame is also a part of the choice-context. In other words, the relevance of choice is related to a certain single or certain multiple time-frames.

And this time-frame aspect of the choice-context is what we call as vision. Vision is the time-frame aspect of the choice-context. Vision is a part of the choice-context.

1.1.3 | Phenomenon of philosophy related | Dissolving of the boundaries between science & philosophy

1.1.3.a | Ultimate purpose is inevitable | It is the absolute limitation of phenomenon of action

As we have explored in previous manuscript 'Knowledge 5', philosophy is a phenomenon related to the ultimate purpose, related to the ultimate vision of purpose. Philosophy is a phenomenon of getting the purpose(s) in alignment with the ultimate purpose. And ultimately, the ultimate purpose is the only purpose. And every other sub-purpose makes sense, i.e. becomes a purpose, only when it is in alignment with the ultimate purpose.

And as we have explored in previous manuscript 'Existence 1', purpose comes before action, and action cannot exist without the existence of the purpose behind the action.

Whatever actions we have taken, are taking and will ever take; there is a purpose to each & every action.

But here is a thing. For every action, there is not just the purpose, but also the ultimate purpose. Whatever purpose you are having, at the core of it is the ultimate purpose.

You can function only in the direction of the ultimate purpose. Choice can only be in alignment with the ultimate purpose This is the absolute limitation of the phenomenon of choice. Ultimate purpose is inevitable.

So whatever you are doing, by-default, you are doing it in the direction of the ultimate purpose. It is the perception you have of ultimate purpose, is what is driving your choices.

But no matter what perception you have related to the ultimate purpose, under-the-hood, it is the same ultimate purpose. You are chasing only one thing, the ultimate purpose. There cannot be any other chase.

This is the absolute limitation of our actions. This is the absolute limitation of the phenomenon of action.

Ultimate purpose is inevitable.

1.1.3.b | The effectiveness of philosophy | 2 factors driving your actions

Philosophy is about perception related to ultimate purpose

As we have explored in previous manuscript 'Knowledge 5', philosophy is the logic related to the purpose. To be precise, philosophy is the logic which brings the alignment between the truth & the perception of truth related to the phenomenon of purpose; which also includes the phenomenon of the alignment between purpose & action.

Philosophy is about the perception related to the ultimate purpose.

2 factors driving your actions

Your action are guided by following 2 factors

1. Primarily by – your philosophy [your perception related to the ultimate purpose]
2. Secondarily by – your perception of existence [your understanding of science]

You are driven by philosophy

As we just explored, being in alignment with the ultimate purpose, is an absolute limitation of the phenomenon of action. And as we have explored in previous manuscript 'Existence 1', in material world, action is inevitable.

Action cannot exist without the purpose.

So here is a thing. Philosophy is involved in your each & every action. You cannot escape action, and you cannot escape philosophy.

At the core of your action is choice.

As we have explored in previous manuscript 'Knowledge 5', philosophy is indirectly about the purpose, and directly about the choice of actions. Consciously or sub-consciously, you do have a philosophy; and that philosophy is driving all your choices, all your actions.

Whole world runs on philosophy

Consciously or subconsciously, you are driven by philosophy. You, as a whole, transform, when your philosophy is transformed to its core.

Consciously or sub-consciously, everyone is driven by philosophy. The whole world runs on philosophy. The chaos of the world is because of philosophy. Either because of wrong philosophy, or right philosophy which is not deep enough, or conflicts of philosophy; or may be because of one or multiple or all of these.

The order and peace of the world, will come only out of philosophy, no where else. Because of the philosophy which would be aligned with the ultimate truth. The whole world will transform, when the philosophy on which the world runs, would transform to its core.

Good & evil is to be found in philosophy, not actions

Two actions might appear to be same at surface level, but when you would dig more into understanding them, they might be two completely different action overall. Two actions might be same in how they are executed, but completely different and opposite in its philosophy.

Example

Let us take an example here. Suppose that, Person A and Person B, both are giving food to a poor and hungry person.

But the purpose of Person A is that, Person A want to make that poor and hungry person, its slave, by burring that poor person under the burden of favor, and also to boost self ego, but the purpose does not include the well-being of that poor person. And the purpose of Person B, is merely the well being of that poor person.

So you see, the action of the Person A, is overall actually an evil action, and the action of Person B is overall a good action, a good deed.

There exists no action, without the purpose for that action. The philosophy behind the action, determines if the action is good or evil.

Good or evil is to be found in philosophy, not action.

1.1.3.c | The only choice we have is being aligned with the ultimate philosophy

You are completely ignorant of what you inevitably want [the ultimate purpose]

As we just explored, the ultimate purpose is inevitable. The only chase is chase of the ultimate purpose. And as we have explored in previous manuscript 'Knowledge 5', philosophy is about the ultimate purpose. Whatever we are doing, we are doing for the sake of achieving the ultimate purpose.

But as we explored just earlier in this manuscript, your action are guided by following 2 factors

1. Primarily by – your philosophy [your perception related to the ultimate purpose]
2. Secondarily by – your perception of existence [your understanding of science]

So it is the perception you have, is what is causing to do whatever you are doing.

The scenario here is, you cannot escape the ultimate purpose; and knowingly or unknowingly, you do want to achieve the ultimate purpose. But due to ignorance involved, though inevitable, you have no idea as what the ultimate purpose really is. So you are driven by something which you have no idea, not of what it is, neither of its existence. At the core of your complete current functioning is, ignorance.

So you are working towards what you inevitably want, but have no idea as what it is that you inevitably want.

Ultimate philosophy related | Ultimate philosophy is the only philosophy

Ultimate philosophy is about developing the clarity related to the ultimate purpose. Ultimate philosophy is about knowing related to the ultimate purpose. It is about getting the perception of truth of the ultimate purpose, in alignment with the truth of the ultimate purpose.

Ultimate philosophy is the philosophy which is based on the bottom-up approach of knowledge.

Ultimate philosophy is the only philosophy

As we have explored just earlier in this manuscript, ultimate purpose is inevitable. The only chase is the chase of the ultimate purpose. And as we have explored in previous manuscript 'Knowledge 5', philosophy is the logic which brings the alignment between the truth & the perception of truth related to the phenomenon of purpose; which also includes the phenomenon of the alignment between purpose & action.

The core of philosophy is knowing related to the ultimate purpose. It is about getting the perception of truth of the ultimate purpose, in alignment with the truth of the ultimate purpose.

Ignorance & mis-alignment cannot be the philosophy.

Philosophy is about knowing. And knowing can only be from the bottom-up approach.

Ultimate philosophy is the only philosophy.

You are driven by superstition

Philosophy which is not from the depth of bottom-up approach, if claimed as philosophy, would be a superstition.

As we have just explored, you cannot escape philosophy. As well as ignorance & mis-alignment cannot be the philosophy.

So if you are functioning based on the notion that this is how things are or how things should be, without the knowing related to the ultimate purpose, then you are driven not by philosophy, but by superstition, superstition related to the ultimate purpose. In that case, what you are calling as philosophy, is a superstition that you have.

We had explored the phenomenon of superstition in previous manuscript 'Knowledge 1'.

To not be driven by superstition, you should be driven by either of the following

1. Understanding of everything based on knowing related to the ultimate purpose, based on bottom-up approach
2. Functioning based on the awareness of the ignorance involved in your perception related to the ultimate purpose

Positivity & negativity related

If you do not have knowing related to the ultimate purpose, in other words, if your philosophy is not the ultimate philosophy, then you have no idea if what you are doing in life, what you want from life, is it really positivity or is negativity.

Whatever choices you are making, you have no idea if those choices are ultimately positive or negative.

The positivity which is in alignment with the ultimate purpose, is the only positivity. As this is in alignment with what you really want.

And the choices which are not in alignment with the ultimate purpose, is negativity. As this is not what you want, so you are making choices against your desires.

If you do not develop clarity related to everything, based on knowledge of the ultimate philosophy, then you remain critically vulnerable to negativity. And you would be critically blocking your potential for positivity.

Meaningful actions related | The only choice we have is being aligned with the ultimate philosophy

As we have explored in previous manuscript 'Knowledge 5', the ultimate purpose is the only purpose. And every other sub-purpose makes sense, i.e. becomes a purpose, only when it is in alignment with the ultimate purpose. Philosophy is a phenomenon of getting the purpose(s) in alignment with the ultimate purpose.

You can understand if the actions you are taking are meaningful or are non-sense, only when you understand its alignment with the ultimate purpose. And for this you would need to have depth of understanding of the choice-context, based on which those actions were chosen.

And you cannot have depth of understanding of the relevant choice-context, without the knowing of ultimate philosophy.

Non-sense actions are negative choices. And to a lesser or greater extent, it does have adverse effect on your pleasure potential. In worst case scenario, it might even critically block your pleasure potential, making you stuck in pain or misery.

So it is important to make positive choices which would lead to meaningful actions. It is important of making every choice an aware & knowledgeable choice.

And for that you need to know & align yourself to the ultimate philosophy.

Ultimate philosophy is the only way to align ourselves to what we really want. So the only choice we have is being aligned with the ultimate philosophy.

1.1.3.d | Core aspects of getting aligned with the ultimate philosophy

The only thing that can get you aligned with the ultimate philosophy is, perception. In other words, all your actions would be in alignment with the ultimate purpose, only through alignment of your perception with the ultimate truth.

As we have explored in previous manuscript 'Knowledge 1', knowledge, ignorance, superstition, belief & faith are all phenomenon related to perception.

Your only target to raise your pleasure potential is, perception.

So your action should not be driven by superstition, but by knowledge of the ultimate purpose.

For your actions to be driven by knowledge of the ultimate purpose, i.e. for all your actions to be meaningful, you need to have clarity about the choice-context of all choices.

And as we have explored just earlier, in the case of choice-context, the base of clarity is knowledge.

So you first need to have knowledge.

As we have explored in previous manuscript 'Existence 1', purpose comes before action, not vice versa.

So the primary knowledge you need to have is the knowledge related to purpose, i.e. knowledge of philosophy [ultimate philosophy]. And after the knowledge related to purpose, you need to have knowledge related to actions. And for that, you need to have knowledge related to existence, from bottom-up approach.

Wrt clarity of the choice-context, there are 2 core aspects. Following are those 2 aspects

1. Purpose
2. Vision

The focus of philosophy [ultimate philosophy] is vision [ultimate vision]. You can figure out the real positivity, only based on the ultimate vision.

And here is a thing about philosophy which we explored in previous manuscript 'Knowledge 5'. It is vision which changes the game completely.

With the change of philosophy, your whole functioning changes, completely. All the actions you take, are with a particular vision (perception), in alignment with the current perception of the ultimate purpose. It is the perception of truth of the ultimate purpose, not the truth of the ultimate purpose. Once the vision wrt the purpose changes, the actions change, as now the choice of actions need to be changed for the actions to be in alignment with the new perception related to the ultimate purpose. And with this, your complete functioning changes. So philosophy changes your entire functioning. Vision changes your entire game of life.

1.1.4 | Dissolving of the boundaries between science & philosophy | The real functioning of existence is, philosophy

Philosophy is involved in everything | The real functioning of existence is, philosophy

As we have explored in previous manuscript 'Knowledge 5', philosophy is a phenomenon related to ultimate purpose. And as we have explored in previous manuscript 'Existence 1', the real underlying mechanism of existence is desire. Purpose & action co-exists. The core of desire is purpose. In other words, core of desire is philosophy.

So as purpose & action co-exists, at the core of every action is philosophy. Everything that is happening, every change that is taking place, is based on philosophy. Philosophy is involved in everything about the existence.

The real functioning of existence is, philosophy.

We being the same mechanism [absolute mechanism] are driven by philosophy [the real functioning of existence]

As we have explored in previous manuscripts of 'Knowledge sub-series', we are the same mechanism, the absolute mechanism, as that of the underlying mechanism of existence. And with the non-sensory direct witness, we witness the underlying mechanism of existence.

And as we have explored just earlier, we are driven by philosophy. Ultimate purpose is inevitable.

So the real functioning of existence is philosophy.

Science & philosophy co-exists | Philosophy is the core of science

As we have explored through previous manuscript 'Knowledge 5', computation is a domain related to the phenomenon of action. And the core of domain of computation is, perception [science]. And as we have explored in previous manuscript 'Existence 1', purpose & action co-exists. And purpose comes before action.

So science & philosophy co-exists. And it is philosophy which comes before science. Philosophy is the core of science. Exploration of philosophy is the core of exploration of functioning of existence.

1.2 | Phenomenon of desire related

1.2.1 | Depth of existence of phenomenon of desire, within us

Desire is the core of our functioning

There is one thing which is at the very core of all our functioning. Now the question is what is that thing ?

It is something which we try to manifest all the time, each and every day of our life, each and every moment of our life.

It is reason because of which we work. It is something because of which we do whatever we do.

It is something which can be a source of our pleasure. But it is also the thing which is the source of our pain.

It is something because of which we evolve. It is something because of which we degrade.

It is something which make sinners, as well as, it is something which makes saints. It is at the very core of our existence.

And that thing is, desire.

We cannot do anything without desire

What do you think, can you do anything without the desire ?

Suppose you want to look on the right side, if you do not desire to look on the right side, to be more precise, if the desire to look on the right side does not

exist within you, at that moment, can you look on the right side ? Can you do it, without the desire ?

The answer is, no.

Suppose that you need to move your hand, can you move your hand, even a little bit, if the desire to move your hand does not exist within you ? Can you do it, without the desire ?

The answer is, no.

You cannot do even a minutest of the things, without the existence of the desire that is causing it to happen.

But the desire is so subtle, that if you won't precisely observe it, you won't even realize it as being a desire.

You cannot stand without desire, you cannot sit without desire, you cannot talk without desire, you cannot run without desire, you cannot walk without desire, you cannot think without desire, you cannot smile without desire, you cannot laugh without desire, you cannot cry without desire.

You cannot do anything without desire.

Desire is the base of our psychology, our emotions, our ambitions, everything. The base of our thinking is only one and only one thing, and that is desire.

Choice related

Just earlier in this manuscript, we explored the critical importance of phenomenon of choice.

At the core of phenomenon of choice is phenomenon of desire. It is for the desire, that we make choices.

Philosophy related

As we just explored, ultimate purpose is inevitable.

Ultimate purpose is a phenomenon related to desire. Ultimate purpose is the ultimate desire. It would be more appropriate to call ultimate purpose as the ultimate truth of your desires.

Reaction related

So this was about action, but what about reactions ? How is reaction a phenomenon related to desire ? For example, when you get angry, but you don't want to get angry. When you cry, but you don't want to cry

In these cases, you desire something, but you are doing something else.

Reactions are the experiences that we have of pain & pleasure, in varying intensities, due to the desires that we have. Whatever desire(s) is causing those reactions, if we would not had those desires, then those reactions would not had existed.

Importance of understanding the phenomenon of desire

Desire is the base of our entire functioning. Each and every single thing that you do, there is desire that exists at the core of that each and everything.

The base of all the miseries and pain within you, is desire. If you want to understand them, understand the desire that is causing them. And if you want to transform them, explore the phenomenon of desire.

If you want to raise your pleasure potential, you need to explored the phenomenon of desire.

Ultimate positivity cannot be achieved without exploring the phenomenon of desire. As to choice what you want, you first need to have knowledge of what you really want.

Wrt meditation, the base of meditation is desire. Meditation cannot be understood without understanding the phenomenon of desire.

Understanding the phenomenon of desire is inevitable for knowledge exploration.

1.2.2 | Desire exists as a complete phenomenon | Desire phenomenon belongs to eternity

Desire exists as a complete phenomenon

Before understanding as what do we really desire, i.e. before exploration of the phenomenon of desire, here are some questions. Why do we desire whatever we desire ? Why do these desire exist ?

But before even these questions, here is a thing. The base of these question is the fact that, 'we desire'.

So, the question here is, are these desires really different kinds of desires, or do they just appear to be of different kinds, on surface level, but under the surface, is it the same thing ?

Are different kinds of desires, really different, or are they variations of the same core desire ?

Here is a thing about desires. Desires are not isolated from one another. All desires are a part of the same phenomenon, phenomenon of desire. Desire exists as compete phenomenon.

As we have explored in previous manuscript 'Knowledge 3', we do not identify phenomenon by variations, but by inherent similarity. There is inherent similarity to all the possible desires.

And all desires are related to this same inherent similarity. All desires are the same inherent similarity.

In other words, no matter what the variation of desire, under-the-hood, it is the same thing.

Desire phenomenon belongs to eternity

Now here is a question. Does the phenomenon of desire has any end, and did it had any start ?

As we have explored in previous manuscript 'Existence 1', creation & destruction does not exists. Existence is about transformation. Everything that exists, exists forever. Material world is a part of eternity. We are in eternity, and material world is an experience that we are having.

Phenomenon of desire is a phenomenon related to eternity. The functioning of phenomenon of desire belongs to eternity.

Whatever we desire, the reason as what we desire it, that reason belong to eternity. Existence of the phenomenon of desire, is in eternity.

Desire is an eternal phenomenon.

1.2.3 | Boundaries to desire are drawn by belief (perception), not desire

Here is a thing about what you can desire, and cannot desire. You can only desire the possibility that you believe is possible. You cannot desire any possibility which you don't believe is possible.

And as we have explored in previous manuscript 'Knowledge 1', belief is a phenomenon related to perception.

Phenomenon of fantasy

Here is what happens in the phenomenon of fantasy. Whenever you fantasize a certain possibility, you perceive that possibility as a possibility, but as an illusionary possibility. And as you perceive it as an illusionary possibility, so you don't desire to manifest it in reality.

But if you start to believe that fantasy as being a real possible, then it won't be a fantasy any more, but a desire. You would desire to manifest it in reality.

Boundaries to desire are drawn by belief [perception], not desire.

To desire something, you need to work, not on desire, but on belief, i.e. perception.

And as we just explored, desire is the core of our functioning.

So to achieve the highest potential of our functioning, the target is not desire, but belief, i.e. perception. Desire will by-default follow the perception.

For us to desire the desires of highest potential, we need to work on belief, i.e. perception.

For us to desire the right desire, i.e. desires in alignment with the ultimate purpose, we need to work on our beliefs, i.e. perception.

Only when we are desiring the desires in alignment with the ultimate purpose, shall we be able to achieve the ultimate purpose.

Only when we are desiring the desires of the highest potential, wrt alignment with the ultimate purpose, shall it be the ultimate positivity.

So alignment of these boundaries, with truth is critical for us to achieve the ultimate purpose, i.e. to achieve what we really want. And for this, we need to explore knowledge, clarity & vision.

1.3 | Phenomenon of pleasure related

1.3.1 | Desire & pleasure related | Pleasure potential related

1.3.1.a | We desire only one thing, pleasure

As we just explored, desire exists as a complete phenomenon. In other words, no matter what the variation of desire, under-the-hood, it is the same thing. There is inherent similarity to all the possible desires. But now the question is, what is that inherent similarity ?

That inherent similarity is, pleasure. You desire one and only one thing, and that is pleasure. That's it, you desire nothing else. Whatever desires you have, under-the-hood it is merely the chase of pleasure.

1.3.1.b | Perception & conditions causes variations of desires | Desire is chase of pleasure

As we have just explored, desire is only about one thing, pleasure. But now the question is, how does so many variations of desires exist ?

Variation of desires is due to varying conditions and varying perception of pleasure. As per your perception of pleasure & your conditions, you are chasing pleasure. Difference between desires of everyone, is only of the conditions & perception, not of what they really are chasing, i.e. pleasure.

As we explored just earlier in this manuscript, whatever you are doing, by-default, you are doing it in the direction of the ultimate purpose. It is the perception you have of ultimate purpose, is what is driving your choices. But no matter what perception you have related to the ultimate purpose, under-the-hood, it is the same ultimate purpose. The ultimate purpose is pleasure.

We can define desire as, chase of pleasure. Desire is chase of pleasure.

1.3.1.c | Every action that we take, its purpose is pleasure | We cannot escape chase of pleasure

As we have explored in previous manuscript 'Existence 1', purpose & action co-exist. And purpose comes before action. That purpose is pleasure.

The core of phenomenon of action is, chase of pleasure.

Every action that you take, every action that exists, is a chase of pleasure.
Every action that exists, is a by-product of chase of pleasure.

In materialistic existence, you cannot escape action, and you cannot escape chase of pleasure.

Example [Purpose-action co-existence]

Let us take an example here.

When you move your hand, you move it because sub-consciously, due to a certain relevant reason, you perceive the current position of your hand, as pain. So you feel the need to move your hand.

And further movement of your hand is guided by either of the following 2 things

1. Getting the hand in some different position than the current position
2. Getting the hand into a desired position

In either of the case, it is chance of pleasure.

Another example would be example of breathing. Like every other action, even the breathing that happens, happens as a chase of pleasure.

But all this is sub-conscious process, which needs sophisticated witness to realize the existence of choice of pleasure in every action that happens.

And these examples are also an additional evidence for coexistence of purpose & action.

1.3.1.d | Example [Taste] | Change of place where you draw pleasure from wrt change of perception

Let us take an example here.

Suppose that there is a certain person who is very foody, who is fond of eating different kinds of tasty food.

That person is so fond of tasty food that, it is the most important purpose of his life. That person lives for experiencing pleasure through food.

So in the quest for the taste, that person desire to explore as many restaurants and places as possible, to explore the variations of taste in same kind of food, and to find out as where is it which has the best taste available for the same food.

That person plans to keep traveling throughout the world, for the sake of food.

He is so foody, that he even developed various means of earning money around this passion of his. His whole life revolves around food, around the passion for achieving the highest of pleasure potential possible, through food.

So what is it, that is happening here ?

Why has food become the core purpose of life for that person ?

And is it possible that this purpose take a complete u-turn ? If yes, then how and when ?

Can this desire of that person change, upside-down ? If yes, then how and when ?

So what is happening here ?

The sole reason for that person to have this kind of extreme passion is, because that person draws pleasure from experiencing the taste, more than anything else. Taste has formed lust for that person.

And note a point here that, it is the taste that has formed the lust, not food. Food is a medium for the taste.

What do you think, if there had been some other means of experiencing taste, other than food, would food had been the sole passion ?

If there had been some other means to experience taste other than food, and if that means would had been far superior than food, then the desire of that person would had been to experience taste through that means, and not food.

Place where you draw pleasure from changes with the change of perception, especially deeper perception

You see, the purpose is the same in this case but the means has changed, from food to that superior means of experiencing taste. So the desire for food has changes, and that new means has formed the desire.

And the thing which has changed here is, perception. And as here the newer perception is deeper than the older perception, the pleasure potential has increased.

Place where you draw pleasure from changes with the change of perception, especially deeper perception.

1.3.1.e | Example [Taste] ...continued | When your philosophy changes, you change completely | Philosophy changes through pain

Let us continue with the example. Now let us come back to the core desire.

How will the core desire for taste, change ?

What if that person stops drawing pleasure from experience of taste, and starts drawing pleasure from only satisfaction of hunger ? Well, that is truly when the desire of that person would change to become upside-down.

Now this is the point when that person's whole purpose of life changes. Now all the desire of travel the whole world for the sake of lust, would come to a halt. And now any healthy food capable of satisfaction of hunger from anywhere, would do the job.

With this the whole purpose of life of that person, would change. And at the core of this change is change of philosophy.

And this change of philosophy is possible only when that person realized the pain of over-indulgence in the experience of taste. In other words, when that person realized the mis-alignment of the current purpose with the ultimate purpose, i.e. pleasure.

As we have explored just earlier in this manuscript, change of your philosophy, changes you completely.

With the change of your philosophy, why do you change completely ?

Because the place where you draw pleasure from, changes, with the change of philosophy.

In this example, the person stopped drawing pleasure from taste, and focused on health.

1.3.1.f | Exploring ultimate philosophy as soon as possible | More deeper the perception, more sustained the pleasure

2 ways of pain realization

As we just explored, deeper perception changes desire. And as we have explored just earlier in this manuscript, change of philosophy is through pain. So now, here is a thing. Pain can be realized through either of the following 2 ways

1. Facing the pain
2. Knowing the pain through Knowledge exploration

Exploring ultimate philosophy as soon as possible

Knowing the pain through knowledge exploration, bypasses the need for facing the pain. And this even aids you into changing your desire & choices, even before you face the pain, thus avoiding the pain.

Note a point that, here I am talking about avoiding of the pain, not the conditions. In other words, manifestations of the relevant conditions may or may not be avoided, but in either of the case, you are immune to the pain.

So we do have a way by which we can bypass the need for facing the pain, to realize it. So why choose the painful way, i.e. way of facing the pain to realize its existence.

And sooner or later, to raise our pleasure potential, the perception has to get deepened, leading to change of philosophy.

The only choice you have is to explore the ultimate philosophy, as soon as possible.

Example [Taste] ...continued

If that person would had deeper perception before, in that case, he would had focused on exploration of new means of experiencing taste, rather than focusing only on one known means i.e. food.

And in that exploration he would had gone deeper into exploration of the truth of phenomenon of taste.

And exploration of the effect of overindulgence in taste, on body, would had made that person realize the pain involved.

With that, if the passion still sustains, then it would not be about mere pleasure from taste, but exploration of the phenomenon of taste for the sake of knowledge exploration. As well as apart from the knowledge exploration of phenomenon of taste, the focus on health, is increased pleasure potential.

More deeper the perception, more sustained the pleasure

More deeper the perception, more sustained the pleasure is.

More surface level the perception, more fragile the pleasure is. In case of surface level perception [perception which lacks necessary depth of knowing], you are drawing pleasure from a fragile place.

With deeper perception, your pleasure potential increases, as you are now able to see the new possibilities.

As we have explored from previous manuscripts of 'Knowledge sub-series', we explore possibilities by exploration of limitations. So first we need to explore the real limitations. And in exploration of real limitations, we first need to explore absolute limitations.

So with exploration of the absolute limitations of the phenomenon of desire & the place where we are drawing pleasure from, we would be able to make relevant choices of greater potential [pleasure potential].

With deeper perception, we would be able to make better choices in alignment with the sustained pleasure.

1.3.1.g | Note [Ultimate pleasure potential related]

Note a point here.

We have explored pleasure potential through an example which we can relate to. Even this increased pleasure potential is far lesser than the ultimate pleasure potential. And that exploration would need exploration of possibilities based on bottom-up approach of knowledge of existence, i.e. exploration of absolute limitations of existence.

1.3.2 | Pleasure & pain related

1.3.2.a | 'Pain & pleasure' exists in mere comparison | Beyond comparison, 'pleasure & pain' exists in some other form

Example [pleasure related]

Let us take an example here.

Suppose that you are a foody person, and you eat a certain unique and very tasty food item, which is more tasty than anything you ate earlier, i.e. before eating this food item. Will you find pleasure in eating that or not ?

Yes you will, of-course.

Why would you find pleasure in eating that food ? What is happening here ? In this case, you are seeking pleasure from experiencing the taste. And the food that you are eating is giving you greater kind of pleasure through taste, than what you had experienced before.

And greater pleasure is pleasure wrt lower pleasure.

Now suppose that now onward's whatever food you eat has that greater level of taste. So after a period of time, it becomes your habit.

Now, will you find pleasure in eating that food ? I am talking about pleasure wrt taste, as you might find pleasure wrt satisfying your hunger. So will you find pleasure wrt taste, in eating that food ?

The answer is no. Now you won't find pleasure wrt taste, in eating that food.

Why won't you find pleasure wrt taste, in eating that food ? What is happening here ?

As compared to previous taste, which was your habit, the new taste was much better, so you were able to enjoy the new better taste. But afterwards, the better taste became habit. So as compared to the new habit of better taste, the same item tastes same as the new habit, not better. So you feel it as normal, not pleasurable, as it is not a better pleasure than the new habit.

So now when you compare the tastes, the taste that you are experiencing, is not greater pleasure, but the same pleasure. So it is not pleasure wrt the pleasure that you experience always.

Example [pain related]

Let us take an example here.

Suppose that, government unfairly increases tax on you by 5% on you. You would find pain in this action of government.

I am saying unfairly because, if it is fair, then you should not find pain in that.

But now suppose that, instead of 5%, government unfairly increases tax by 20% on you, then you would find extreme pain in that.

And now suppose that, after a period of time, from that increased 20%, government reduces the tax by 15%. Now what ?

Now, if you would not analyze the things precisely, to figure out as what is happening; in that case, you would feel happy that such a huge amount of tax is reduces.

And if government gives you back the 15% extra, of the 20% which you had paid earlier, in that case, you would say that government is so good.

But actually what happened here is that, government wanted to increase the tax unfairly by 5% without making you realize the pain of it. So it gave you greater pain, to make it as a reference. And with respect to that reference, anything lesser than that, would appear to be pleasure. So ultimately government achieved its goal of unfairly increasing the tax and also tricked you into being happy with that action.

So by giving you the wrong reference, now even the pain appears as pleasure. But with the right reference, you would understand the pain, the truth in this situation.

'Pain & pleasure' exists in mere comparison

Lesser pain is pleasure as compared to greater pain. Greater pain is pain as compared to lesser pain.

Greater pleasure is pleasure as compared to lesser pleasure. Lesser pleasure is pain as compared to greater pleasure.

And here is one more thing. Pain & pleasure on its own is neither pain nor pleasure.

Pain & pleasure cannot be pain and pleasure respectively, on their own, i.e. if not compared to each other.

Pain & pleasure are pain & pleasure respectively only when compared to each other. Pain & pleasure exists based on mere comparison.

Beyond comparison, 'pleasure & pain' exists in some other form

As we have explored in previous manuscripts of 'Knowledge sub-series', in the case where a certain phenomenon exists based on mere comparison, in that case, that phenomenon does exist, but in some other form, not in the form in which we witness it, i.e. based on mere comparison. And even though it exists in some other form, the absolute limitations stay the same, even beyond the comparison.

We witness the phenomenon of pleasure & pain, based on mere comparison. So phenomenon of pleasure & pain does exist, but not in the form in which we know it.

We will explore as to what exactly is pleasure & pain, further in this manuscript.

1.3.2.b | Pleasure is an absolute limitation of desire

We cannot choose pain | Choosing pleasure is an absolute limitation of our desires

As we just explored, with deeper perception, desire changes. And as we explored just earlier in this manuscript, desire is all about pleasure. So now the question, with the ultimate depth of perception, can the most core thing, i.e. chase for pleasure, also change into chase of pain ? What if you consciously want to choose pain ? And if you did consciously choose pain, then is not desire also about pain ? If someone desires to choose pain, then desire is also about pain, and not merely about pleasure, right ? And you have, at some point in life, consciously chosen pain, right ?

Well think again. Whatever you had chosen, did you really perceived it as pain ? Surely, you might had perceived it as pain. But, as we explored just earlier in this manuscript, lesser pain is pleasure wrt greater pain. So, whatever you had chosen, did you really perceived it as pain ? If no, then did you really choose pain ?

So had you even in your entire life, even once, chosen pain ? Can you really choose pain even if you want to ? Is it really possible to do that ?

Example

Let us take an example here.

For the sake of loved ones, a person chooses pain for self. So in this case, has that person chosen pain ?

The answer is, no. In this case, that person draws more pleasure from well being of loved one than the well being of self. So for that person, well being of loved ones, is greater pleasure than the well being of self. For that person, pain for loved ones is greater pain then the pain for self.

So in this case, even if that person is choosing pain for self, but that pain is a lesser pain, so a is a pleasure. And not choosing that pain for the loved ones would had been greater pain than the pain which that person has chosen for self.

So even if it appears that this person is choosing pain for self, but in reality, that person is choosing pleasure.

Example

Let us now take another example.

A person might want to explore how a certain pain feels like, so that person chooses the pain. So is that person really choosing the pain ?

The answer is, no. In this case, for that person, not exploring how that pain feels like, is greater pain, than going through that pain. So that person is choosing a lesser pain of experiencing the pain, than greater pain of not knowing as how that pain feels like. And lesser pain is pleasure, as compared to greater pain. So even if it might appear that, that person is choosing pain, but in reality that person is perceiving it as pleasure, and hence choosing pleasure, not pain.

You can only choose pleasure. You cannot choose pain; it is not impossible.

You can choose pain, only if it does disguise itself, as pleasure.

So to be precise, you cannot choose something, which you perceive as pain.

You can only choose the thing which you perceive as pleasure.

We can choose only pleasure, and this is the absolute limitation of our desires. Desiring pain, is an illusionary idea.

No one can make you choose pain

No one can make you choose pain by force

But what if someone forces you to choose pain ? Is it possible ? What happens when someone forces you to do something ?

When someone forces you to do something which you don't want to do, in that case that person brings in the concept of consequences. That person make you to choose between consequences and doing the thing. So basically that person makes you to choose between lesser pain and greater pain.

So now here comes the phenomenon of desire preference level. Which one of these options would be lesser pain and which one would be greater pain, would depend on the preference level of your desires.

If not facing the consequences is at higher preference than doing the thing, then you would choose not to do the thing. If doing the thing is of higher preference than the consequences, or if not getting influenced or manipulated, or something else, is of higher preference level than facing the consequences, then you would not care about the consequences. Or even if you would be scared of the consequences, but still you would do it.

No one can even convince you into choosing pain

But now you might say that, 'no one can make me choose pain by force, but what if someone does convince me into choosing pain?'

No one can even convince you into choosing pain.

How can anyone convince you into choosing pain? How is it possible?

Even when someone is trying to convince you into choosing something, then in that case, that person will have to make that thing to appear as pleasure in your perception.

So basically you would be choosing pain, only if it is in disguise as pleasure.

But even in that case, is not 'choosing pain'.

1.3.3 | Nature of pleasure – [State of pleasure | Peak of pleasure]

1.3.3.a | Importance of understanding nature of pleasure | State of pleasure & peak of pleasure

Importance of understanding nature of pleasure

To understand the phenomenon of desire, it is critical to understand the nature of desire. As exactly what type of pleasure do you want?

But are there types to pleasure. I am not talking about the variation, I am talking about the types related to the base. I am talking about the pleasure as a phenomenon.

Here is a thing. There indeed are the types to pleasure.

And there is a type of pleasure which you are looking for, which you desire.

As we explored earlier in this manuscript, desire is chase of pleasure. In chase of pleasure, understanding of the nature of pleasure that we want to chase, changes the game of life completely.

As we have explored through previous manuscript 'Knowledge 5', it is vision that changes the game of life, completely.

Vision is a phenomenon related to this nature of pleasure.

State of pleasure & peak of pleasure

Nature of pleasure are of two types; there are 2 types of pleasure. Following are those 2 types

1. Peak of pleasure
2. State of pleasure

So here we are bring two new and important terminologies into use, state of pleasure & peak of pleasure.

To understand the nature of pleasure precisely, you should understand the difference between the peak of pleasure and the state of pleasure.

Peak of pleasure, is the pleasure that gets elevated, but is not sustained in that elevated state, endlessly. Peak of pleasure has a start and an end.

State of pleasure, is the pleasure that gets elevated, but is sustained in that elevated state, endlessly.

1.3.3.b | You want to achieve – state of pleasure, not peak of pleasure | Everything is aspiring for state of pleasure

In previous video, we coined and defined two new terms, which are the types of nature of pleasure. So the nature of pleasure are of 2 types. One is peak of pleasure and the other one is state of pleasure. And you do want a particular type of pleasure.

So what do you want, do you want to have peak of pleasure or state of pleasure ?

You try hard to make your life secured; why ?

You want to achieve growth in life, and to achieve that growth, you would give up on temporary pleasures, no matter how pleasurable they are; why ?

When you achieve success, when you achieve growth, you want it to be maintained, may be forever, if possible, but you are not ready to give up on that and let it go vanish; why ?

You look for sustained health, and to get that, you are ready to go through pain of exercise, pain of giving up on eating the unhealthy food that you like too much; why ?

To achieve something, you are ready to give up pleasure of comfort, and ready to take up on getting into discipline; why ?

You are afraid of death, may be to a lesser or greater extent, but you are. You do not want to die, why ?

Whatever that you love truly, you do not want it to change or get lost or over, why ?

Because, the type of pleasure that you want is, state of pleasure, and not peak of pleasure.

As we have explored just earlier in this manuscript, for determining the nature of choice, we are focused on future conditions.

Why ? Because, what we want is not the peak of pleasure, but state of pleasure. We want atleast the current pleasure be sustained.

Everything is aspiring for state of pleasure

As we have explored earlier, everything is driven by the same ultimate purpose.

Ultimate purpose is chase of state of pleasure. Everything in existence is aspiring for state of pleasure.

1.3.3.c | Multiple peaks to create illusion of state of pleasure

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As we just explored, we want to achieve state of pleasure. We don't want the peak of pleasure.

But there are times, when we are focused on achieving peak of pleasure rather than the state of pleasure. For example, listening to music, watching movie, doing adventure, enjoying vacations, etc. We might even have certain dreams related to doing a certain task, even if it happens to be done only once in life, and then it is completely over.

So as we see in above examples, there are a lot of times, when we go for peak of pleasure, knowing that it is peak of pleasure, and not the state of pleasure, why does that happen ? If we are choosing peak of pleasure, then how is it that we do not want peak of pleasure ?

As we have just explored, we can only choose something which we perceive as pleasure, we cannot choose something which we perceive pain.

And if sometimes we are focused on achieving peak of pleasure, that means we also perceive peak of pleasure as more pleasure over the state of pleasure, right ? That itself means that we also want peak of pleasure, right ?

Answer

Wrong. It might appear that you want peak of pleasure, but you do not.

Here is what is happening. When you achieve a peak of pleasure, you think that your state of pleasure is increased because you would be satisfied after achieving that peak of pleasure.

But how can a peak of pleasure satisfy you ? How can it elevate your state of pleasure ?

No it is not possible. Because, it is peak of pleasure, and not the state of pleasure. So it would be over, after it is done.

So where does this satisfaction from peak of pleasure, comes from ? How is it possible ?

Well, the satisfaction that you get from the peak of pleasure, you do not get it from a single peak of pleasure. You get that satisfaction through attaining the same peak of pleasure, again and again and again, multiple times, on continuous basis, whenever you desire to.

And that attaining of the peak of pleasure, multiple times, might be actual attainment or attainment through memory.

So here is what is actually happening here. You are trying to create an illusion of state of pleasure by attaining the peak of pleasure multiple times, on continuous basis.

Even though you might not have actual attainment of the peak of pleasure at your disposal, but if you are able to attain that peak of pleasure through memory, then it creates an illusion of state of pleasure by being available for you to be attained whenever you want, through memory.

But it is an illusion of state of pleasure, not state of pleasure. It is still the peak of pleasure.

1.3.3.d | Peak of pleasure, on its own, is futile | Everything is aspiring for state of pleasure [the ultimate purpose]

As we explored just earlier in this manuscript, what we want is, state of pleasure, and not peak of pleasure. And we try to create an illusion of state of pleasure by attaining the peak of pleasure multiple times, on continuous basis. So now, the question is, what if we are not able to achieve that peak of pleasure again and again, ever again ? In that case, what ?

If there is a peak of pleasure which you know that, it would not give you any satisfaction for future, and if may be you would not even remember it at all; will you want to go for it ? On this, you might say, why not !

But if I add one more condition to this. And the condition is that, that peak of pleasure would lower your state of pleasure. Now what ? Would you want to go for it, even now ?

The answer is no, you won't. Unless & until it is out of some habit. As we just explored, you do perceive peak of pleasure as lesser pleasure, if not pain. So ultimately you perceive peak of pleasure as pain.

So here is a thing. Peak of pleasure that does not elevate the state of pleasure, at all, such peak of pleasure does not matter at all, beyond the time frame of that peak of pleasure. In that case, achieving that peak of pleasure or not achieving that peak, in the past, is the same thing. After you are done with the peak of pleasure which does not raise state of pleasure at all, then beyond that peak of pleasure, you are left with no gains at all, if not losses.

Peak of pleasure, on its own, is futile. So what matters is, the state of pleasure, not the peak of pleasure.

And, note a point here. As peak of pleasure, on its own, is futile, so is the negative peak of pleasure, i.e. peak of pain. Peak of pain, on its own, is futile.

And here is a thing. There might happen to be a certain condition, where, not choosing peak of pleasure, would eventually lower the state of pleasure. In that case, what ?

If not choosing the peak of pleasure would lower your state of pleasure, then choosing peak of pleasure, is choosing state of pleasure.

Everything that you do, whatever you do, you do it because, you perceive it as aiding your state of pleasure.

Whatever you do, apart from the most core desire, might be state of pleasure or might be peak of pleasure, but, at the very core, you are chasing state of pleasure. That core desire cannot be peak of pleasure.

As we have explored just earlier in this manuscript, ultimate purpose is pleasure, and desire is chase of pleasure.

But to be precise, here is a thing. Ultimate purpose is about state of pleasure. And desire is chase of state of pleasure.

Everything is aspiring for state of pleasure

As we explored just earlier in this manuscript, we cannot escape chase of pleasure. And as we explored earlier in this manuscript, ultimate purpose is inevitable. Everything is driven by the common ultimate purpose.

And that ultimate purpose is state of pleasure.

As we have explored in previous manuscript 'Existence 1', everything is aspiring for alignment state of being.

And that alignment state of being is state of pleasure. Everything material world, is aspiring for state of pleasure. Everything that is happening, is happening out of aspiration for state of pleasure.

1.3.3.e | Peak of pleasure can never be converted into state of pleasure

As we just explored, we case state of pleasure, not peak of pleasure. Everything that we do, whatever we do, we do it because we perceive it as aiding our state of pleasure. And even through peak of pleasure, we try to create an illusion of state of pleasure by attaining the peak of pleasure multiple times, on continuous basis.

So we want state of pleasure, but it is so very hard to get rid of peak of pleasure, out of our conditioning of needs & habits. So we, many a times, or may be maximum number of times, want to go for peak of pleasure.

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But now the question is, are those the only options that we have; the options to choose between either of the peak of pleasure or the state of pleasure ? Or, can we not have a third option, like, having best of both the worlds ? In other words, how about if we would keep going for peak of pleasure and slowly transition them into state of pleasure, how would that be like; the option to convert peak of pleasure into state of pleasure ?

Answer

Well, that would definitely be a better option, but, such an option does not exists.

With peak of pleasure, by achieving multiple peak of pleasure, multiple times, whenever you want, on continuous basis; you can create an illusion of state of pleasure. But it would still be an illusion of state of pleasure, not state of pleasure.

And this illusion cannot be transformed into reality. Peak of pleasure can never be converted into state of pleasure. Peak of pleasure can never become state of pleasure.

Only when you give up on peak of pleasure, shall you be able to achieve higher state of pleasure. Only when you give up on the peak of pleasure, shall you be able to achieve the state of pleasure.

1.3.3.f | Peak of pleasure is state of pleasure wrt small time frame – state of pleasure is peak of pleasure wrt larger time frame

Peak of pleasure is state of pleasure wrt time-frame equal to or smaller than period of existence of peak

So while exploring the ultimate purpose, we are distinguishing between peak of pleasure and state of pleasure. We now know the exact difference between them; or do we ?

As we have explored just earlier in this manuscript, the most important & critical factor in determining the nature of choice, is time-frame.

When there is a peak of pleasure, there is a certain time period for which that peak lasts.

Now, what if we restrict, or consider a time frame which is only as long as the existence of the peak of the peak of pleasure ? In that case, would it be a peak of pleasure wrt that smaller time frame ?

No, in this case, for that time period, the peak of pleasure, remains the same. So, how would it be called as a peak ? Wrt this smaller time frame, the peak of pleasure, is no more a peak of pleasure, but is a state of pleasure.

The perceived peak of pleasure is state of pleasure wrt time-frame equal to or smaller than period of existence of peak of peak of pleasure.

State of pleasure is peak of pleasure wrt time-frame larger than period of existence of state

?

Now the question is, what if we make our time frame larger, larger than the period of existence of the state of state of pleasure ? Would whatever we are perceiving as state of pleasure, be a state of pleasure wrt to this extremely larger time frame ? Or would it turn out to be a peak of pleasure wrt this extremely larger time frame ?

Answer

Wrt the time frame which is larger than the period of existence of what we are perceiving as the state of state of pleasure, the perceived state of pleasure is no more a state of pleasure, but a peak of pleasure.

Absolute state of pleasure & non-absolute state of pleasure | Ultimate purpose is about absolute state of pleasure

So what really is the nature of a particular pleasure that we are pursuing, depends on the time frame that we are considering. But the thing which appears to be state of pleasure, might turn out to be peak of pleasure wrt the greater time frame. And vice versa.

Now the question is, what time frame should we choose ? Because what peak pleasure to give up on in order to achieve the state of pleasure, depends on that.

But still whatever time frame we choose, if it is lesser than the ultimate time frame, then whatever state of pleasure you would be achieving, would still be a peak of pleasure, as compared to the state of pleasure of the ultimate time frame.

And as we just explored, desire is change of state of pleasure, not peak of pleasure.

State of pleasure wrt ultimate time frame, is the real state of pleasure, the absolute state of pleasure. Every other state of pleasure, is non-absolute state of pleasure, i.e. state of pleasure wrt reference, i.e. based on mere comparison. Rather the state of pleasure which exists, no matter what the time frame, and even beyond the time itself, i.e. even beyond mere comparison, is the real state of pleasure, the absolute state of pleasure, the eternal state of pleasure.

As we explored just earlier in this manuscript, ultimate purpose is inevitable. Ultimate purpose is about absolute state of pleasure. Desire is chase of the absolute state of pleasure.

As we explored in previous manuscript 'Knowledge 5', vision changes the game of life completely.

This is because, with vision, we are able to realize as what is the really is state of pleasure & what really is the peak of pleasure. And by-default we choose the state of pleasure.

?

Now the question is, what is absolute state of pleasure, as ultimately it is the only pleasure ?

We will explore the answer to this question, through further explorations of this manuscript as well as through further manuscript 'Existence 3'.

2 | Part B

Philosophical theory of everything |
The philosophical ultimate-closure [circularity] of everything

2.1 | Phenomenon of ego related

2.1.1 | What do I mean when I say GOD ?

Before going ahead, let me explain as what do I mean when I mention the terms 'GOD'. This is important so as not to cause any confusion related to this term, as we would be talking about the phenomenon of GOD.

With the term GOD, I do not mean GOD as per any religion's perception of GOD. With the term GOD, I mean the universal consciousness, the greater consciousness.

As we have explored through previous manuscripts of 'Knowledge sub-series', we are the same mechanism, as that of the underlying mechanism of existence. In other word, we & the underlying mechanism of existence is the same absolute mechanism.

So when I say greater consciousness, i.e. GOD, I mean the underlying mechanism of existence.

We and GOD together are the ultimate mechanism of existence. We are a part of GOD.

We will explore more about the phenomenon of GOD, in further manuscript 'Existence 3'.

2.1.2 | Introducing ego [Philosophical theory of everything]

2.1.2.a | Criteria for philosophical theory of everything

This manuscript is about the philosophical theory of everything.

Here when we are talking about everything, we are talking about everything related to material world.

As we have explored in previous manuscript 'Knowledge 5', philosophy is a phenomenon related to purpose. Philosophy is about achieving of the ultimate purpose.

So when we are talking about philosophy, we are talking about the mis-alignment state of being.

And as we will explore through further explorations of this manuscript, as well as in further manuscript, material world is a mis-aligned state of being. So everything in philosophical theory of everything has to be the material world.

Philosophical theory of everything is the core reason for existence of material world.

2.1.2.b | Introducing ego [Philosophical theory of everything]

Introducing ego

Everything about you, about your entire materialistic existence, narrows down to one single thing, one thing alone. That's it, one thing !

Everything revolves around that one thing. Everything is because of that one thing.

This entire materialistic existence, is because of that one thing. Period !

When you would understand this one thing to its deepest depth possible, it would reveal everything about the core of functioning of material world.

So now the question is, what is that one thing ?

Here is an introduction of the greatest of all villains. In-fact, it is the only villain. It is the only evil, the only ugliness, the only misery, the only criminal, the only devil.

It is the only enemy that GOD has.

It is the only enemy that karma keeps check on.

We will explore more about the phenomenon of GOD & karma, in further manuscript 'Existence 3'.

But most dangerous and the most frightening thing that this villain has achieved is that, it has hijacked consciousness of each and everyone of us in this materialistic world. We are under its influence, continuous influence.

The name of that villain is, EGO !

Ego is philosophical theory of everything

Life is a mystery. Why are we here, what are we doing here ? Whatever we do, at the core of it all, does it has some genuine meaning, or is it all just a giant timepass.

Where are we heading ? Is there any direction, the direction in which we are heading, or are we direction-less ? If we are direction-less, then shall we keep moving or shall we stop and think on it ? And if we are moving in a certain direction, then what is that direction ? Is that right direction or is it a wrong direction ? What is right direction ?

And in whatever we do, what do we have to gain in it ? And at what cost ? What do we loose in the chase ? Is the gain, worth the loss ? And whatever we think, we would gain from doing what we do, do we really gain it, from doing what we do, or does it merely appears that we would gain from doing what we do ?

But before that, the question is, what is it that we really want, ultimately ? Are we even aware as what do we really want ultimately ? Or do we think that we should want, what we desire now, based on what other want or what others think we should want ? And if we really want something, apart from the influence of others, then the question is, how deeply do we understand our desires ? Do we understand our own desires, to the deepest depth possible, or do we have just surface level understanding of our desires ?

But the more bigger question is, why is it that we want ? Why does this want exists ? Why do we desire ? Why does the phenomenon of desire exist ? Can we not just become desire-less ? Or is desire an end-less phenomenon ? But the big question is, what is desire ?

The answers to all these questions, as well as many more philosophical question related to our existence, is in only one thing, ego.

But you know why ? The life that you are living in the material world, is not your story. This is the story of ego; ego as a complete phenomenon. Our life story is mere a variation of the same story, the story of ego.

Phenomenon of ego is the philosophical theory of everything. Ego is the core reason for existence of material world.

2.1.3 | Journey of ego

2.1.3.a | Ego is a complete phenomenon | Ego has its roots in eternity | Note

Ego is a complete phenomenon

You might think of ego as, excessive pride, arrogance of considering yourself as superior, self-obsession, etc. You are right, it is ego, but it is a part of what ego is, and not what ego is as a whole. Ego is not mere what you think it is, ego as a complete phenomenon, is much more than that.

Ego exists as a complete phenomenon.

Note

Note a point here that, whenever I would be talking about ego, I would be talking about ego as a complete phenomenon, i.e. ego as a whole.

Ego has its roots in eternity

As we have explored in previous manuscript 'Existence 1', this [the existence we are in] is eternity. The functioning belongs to eternity.

So here is a thing. Ego as a complete phenomenon, does not have its roots in this materialistic existence, but in eternity.

Note [Ego operating in you, is you]

Note a point here that, ego operating in you is not something else which is operating, it is you.

I would refer to ego as a whole, as a phenomenon that takes place within you, but, to whatever extent is ego operating within you, it is operating with the permission of your freewill.

So basically, your ego is nothing but your choice. Ego operating in you is you.

2.1.3.b | Ego is a journey, towards ultimate goal of ego | Journey of ego is not restricted to this lifetime

Phenomenon of ego is a journey, towards ultimate goal of ego

Phenomenon of ego is a journey. And this journey is in the direction of ego, the ultimate goal of ego.

As we just explored, the life that you are living in the material world, is not your story, but the story of ego as a complete phenomenon. The journey of your life, is a part of journey of ego.

You are walking that journey now. You are somewhere in that journey. You might not identify with the entire journey, especially the extremes of ego, but if you are walking the path of ego, if you are on the journey of ego, then you are heading in the direction of the extremes of ego.

As we have explored earlier in this manuscript, desire exists in the possibilities that you believe are possible. Boundaries to desire, are drawn by belief, not desire.

So you might not identify with the extremes of ego, as you are restricted by the beliefs of those extremes, as not being possible. But as soon as the possibility of the extremes of ego would prove themselves as being possible, the desire for extremes of ego would come into existence within you. The extremes of ego would manifest itself in you, especially if you are under the absolute influence of ego.

Walking the path of ego is walking in the direction of the ultimate goal of ego, the extremes of ego. As phenomenon of ego is a journey towards the ultimate goal of ego.

Everything in material world is walking the same journey | Journey of ego is not restricted to this lifetime

Everything in material world is walking the same journey, the journey of ego. Some may have chosen the direction of ego-lessness, but even if their journey is in opposite direction towards ego-lessness, but the road still remains the same. And this absolute ego-lessness, the influence of ego still persists.

Whatever ego is acting within all of us, it is all the same phenomenon. It might not have reached its extremes, may be because you didn't get opportunity to grow it to its extremes, or may be because you are already successful in

controlling it and cutting it to a smaller size. Depending on these factors, ego may seem to vary in individuals.

But, no matter what the variation, ego as a whole, is the same phenomenon; it is the same evil.

As I just mentioned, the journey of your life, is a part of journey of ego.

So this life is a part of journey of ego, not the whole journey of ego. Journey of ego is not restricted to this lifetime, but spans over multiple lifetime.

As we have explored in previous manuscript, creation & destruction are an illusionary idea; existence is about transformation. And everything that exists, exists forever.

Note [Use of the terms 'I' & 'you', wrt ego]

Note a point here. While exploring the phenomenon of ego, wrt ego, I might be saying 'I' as well as 'you'. But when I say, 'I' or 'you', in the context of ego, both are the same thing. When I say 'you', it is me talking about your ego, and when I say "I", wrt ego, it is me addressing ego, on behalf of you, for you. So wrt ego, when I say 'I' and 'you', it is both the same thing, i.e. addressing ego, to be precise, your ego.

No matter whose ego, ego as a phenomenon, is the same thing.

2.1.3.c | Journey of ego, stage 3 – 'I am !' | Ego is all about you

Now the question is, what is the ego all about ?

At the core of the phenomenon of ego is, you. Ego is all about you.

This is the first thing to understand about the phenomenon of ego.

And this understanding of ego is related to the stage 3 in the journey of ego.

And that stage is 'I am !'. 'I am', in other words is 'I exist'.

Only when I am, everything else related to me, is. So for everything related to me, to exist, first I should exist. 'I am' is desire to exist.

You want to exist. Even if you die, you want to exist in the memories of people. You want to be remembered, you do not want to be forgotten.

Only when ego exists, shall it have any hopes to achieve its ultimate goal.

As we have explored earlier in this manuscript, we desire state of pleasure, not peak of pleasure.

Ego wants to exist, forever.

This might seem to be the starting point of the journey of ego, and it is somewhat the starting point, but it is not the core of ego, the real starting point.

We will explore the core of ego, i.e. stage 1 & 2, just further in this manuscript. Stage 3 of journey of ego is the starting point of the journey of ego in this materialistic existence. This is where ego enters the realm of materialistic existence.

Note

Note a point here, that while existing in material world, the separate which exists from GOD, is non-absolute separateness.

As we have explored in previous manuscripts of 'Knowledge sub-series', absolute separateness is an illusionary idea.

2.1.3.d | Note [Ego at its core is you (but not real you); but you (the real you) at core are not ego]

Note a point here. Core of the phenomenon of ego is you, but you at core, are not ego. You are beyond ego. And ego state of being is mere a variation of your state of being.

We will explore the core variations of state of being, i.e, ego & ego-lessness, in further manuscript 'Existence 3'.

Ego at its core is you. but not the real you. There is a distinction between you in ego, and the real you.

We will explore this distinction, just further in this manuscript.

2.1.3.e | Journey of ego, stage 4 – 'I am what ?' [Identity] | Identity is oxygen of ego

After 'I am !', the question comes, I am but 'who am I ?'

What is my name ? Where do I belong ? Which is my country ? What is my history ? Who are my ancestors ? Which family do I belong ? Who are my parents ? Who are my siblings ? Who is my spouse ? Who are my relatives ? Who are my friends ? What is my profession ? What are my hobbies ? What are my achievements ? What are my aspirations ? What is my talent ? How many people do know me ? Etc.

We identify ourselves with several factors.

So basically, the question is, I am, but who am I ? What is my identity ?
You need identity. You desire to have prominent identity. You chase identity.
You work for identity. You live for identity.

Having no identity feels pain, you perceive it as pain.
You want to be someone. You cannot live being absolutely nobody. You would even dedicate your whole life, your whole being, to be somebody.

Can you pinpoint any of your desire, which is not at all linked to your identity, directly or indirectly ?
May be you can, but it is hard & rare, as it need you to be immune to the influence of ego, to a lesser or greater extent.

So the stage 4 of the journey of ego is 'I am what ?', i.e. identity.
As we just explored, ego wants to exist, forever.
And for ego to exist, it needs identity. Ego cannot live without it.
Identity is oxygen of ego.

2.1.3.f | Journey of ego, stage 5 – 'Who else is ?' [Comparison to assure difference in identities] | Comparison & difference are food (energy source) of ego

Here is a question. How would it be if everything was similar ? If everyone would had looked the same ? If everyone would had same intelligence ? If everyone would had the same financial status ? If everyone would had same giant success ? If everyone would be equally super rich ? If everyone would be same physically ? If everyone would had the same vehicle ? If everyone would had similar home ? If everyone would had same clothes ? Etc.

How would it be, if everything about everyone, would had been extremely similar ?

In such a scenario, how would we satisfy our ego ? How would we satisfy our need for identity ?

Does similarity satisfy the purpose of identity or does dissimilarity satisfy the purpose of identity ?

It is dissimilarity that satisfy the purpose of identity.

The state 5 in the journey of ego is 'Who else is ?', i.e. comparison of identities to assure the existence of difference.

The core purpose of identity is, to be different, to be unique. How would our ego be satisfied, if there is no difference ?

Ego needs identity, but with difference..

The purpose of having identity, itself becomes void, if the difference does not exist at all.

As we just explored, identity is oxygen of ego.

So, if identity is the oxygen of ego, then comparison & difference are the food of ego, the energy source of ego.

2.1.3.g | Journey of ego, stage 6 – 'Acceptance from all, forever' [firm grounds for achieving its (ego's) monstrous goal] | Without strategy, ego cannot stand rejection from anyone

After the stage 6 of journey of ego, i.e. after assurance of difference of identities, the base is created for ego to survive & to achieve its goal.

But ego needs one more thing for this base to be made rock solid firm. And that is what the stage 6 is about.

Now here are some questions, especially if you are under the influence of ego. What is that one thing that you fear the most, more than even death (if at all) ? What is that one thing that you worry the most about ? What is that one thing which your choices depend on ? What is that one thing that you perceive as being the core need of your life ?

That one thing is, acceptance.

Ego needs acceptance. And it needs acceptance to such an extent that ego dedicates its whole existence towards gaining the acceptance of others. That is why ego works towards earning recognition's, as recognition is established acceptance, which ego perceives as immunity to rejection. If not recognition, then ego will work towards atleast to get fit into the norms of acceptance. Even if rejection comes its way, ego would work towards converting it into acceptance.

Ego fears rejection to such an extent that, even when no one is looking, it behaves as if everyone is looking. And behaves in such a way that it would not get to face established rejection, if not any rejection at all.

As we just explored, ego needs acceptance.
And it needs acceptance, not just from a few, but from all.

If at all ego gets to face rejection from anyone, then it uses strategy(s) to deal with rejection.

The strategies are as follows

1. By rejecting the rejection itself and/or the one rejecting
2. By taking it for granted that eventually, due to certain reason(s), the rejection would change into acceptance
3. Etc

Ego cannot stand rejection without the use of any these strategies. Without these strategies, ego would get brutally crumbled.

Ego can somehow sustain non-absolute rejection, but not absolute rejection.

The worst fear ego has is, facing established rejection, i.e. rejection with no hope of acceptance ever, and no strategy being functioning.

Ego might pretend that it does not care about acceptance, but it does. And it is doing so, i.e. pretending, based on the use of strategy(s).

It is only ego-lessness which can give up on worrying about acceptance of others.

As we have explored earlier in this manuscript, we desire state of pleasure, not peak of pleasure.

So ego want acceptance from all; and it wants it forever.

2.1.3.h | Journey of ego, stage 7 – 'Chase & preservation of superiority, forever' and 'preservation of superiority-inferiority framework, forever' | Preservation of inferiority for self, is also ego

Chase & preservation of superiority, forever

Till the stage 6, ego has ensured that the grounds for its existence as well as for achieving its monstrous goal, are firm. Now it need not to worry about the bare minimum of its existence.

Now what do you think would be the next stage in the journey of ego ? When being under the influence of ego, what would you do after you gain all the necessary recognition's ?

You want massive success, you want status, you want a top-class career, you want to be extremely rich, you want to be famous, you want to be better, in

fact, you want to be the best of all, if possible, the only & irreplaceable greatest of all times.

You don't want to be number two, you want to be number one, the one and only.

As we explored just earlier, difference is food (energy source) of ego.

And if the identities are not similar, then one of them has to be superior, and the other will be inferior. So what do you think ego would want, the superior one, or the inferior one ?

Ego will choose superiority.

As we have explored just earlier in this manuscript, we want state of pleasure, not peak of pleasure.

So after the stage 6, i.e. acceptance, is taken care of, ego wants to chase superiority, and after superiority is attained, it wants to preserve it forever.

The state 7 in the journey of ego is, chase & preservation of superiority, forever.

Preservation of inferiority for self, is also ego

There happens to be cases where ego tries to preserve inferiority for self. So the question here is, how can ego desire inferiority if through this, it cannot achieve its monstrous goal ?

This can happen out of the following reasons.

- 1 Desire for preservation of framework of superiority-inferiority, to preserve the ambition of ego
 - Because, if this framework is destroyed, then how would ego chase its ultimate goal, as this structure is the base of that goal. Only with the existence of this framework, can ego have hopes to eventually get to the position of superiority. Without this framework the ambition of ego crumbles.
- 2 Preservation of currently established framework of superiority-inferiority
 - Acceptance of inferiority aids in preservation of this currently established framework. So that it would execute superiority onto the perceived more inferiors than itself. In this case, ego draws pleasure from this. And as belief that monstrous goal is not possible, blocks ego from looking at acceptance of inferiority (rejection) as pain.

- 3 Out of mere superstition or belief, i.e. perception of how things are, or should be
 - a As we have explored earlier in this manuscript, boundaries to desire are drawn by belief [perception]. The perception that ego has, draws the boundaries on the desires of ego. If the perception of ego does not allow to not be inferior, then it will accept inferiority.
 - b As we explored just earlier, ego cannot stand rejection. Ego cannot stand rejection, only when it comes within the boundaries of its desire. Superstition can block ego from perceiving it [not being inferior] as even a possibility.
- 4 For the sake of preserving the condition, out of the resistance to change
 - o As we have explored earlier in this manuscript, boundaries to desire are drawn by belief [perception]. And as we have explored from previous manuscripts of 'Knowledge sub-series', core of perception is its flawlessness. Wrt the perception that ego has, ego is already set on drawing pleasure based on that perception. So anything that is not aligned with the flawlessness of its perception, disrupts its pleasure. And to preserve this flawlessness, ego will even accept inferiority

Acceptance of inferiority is also ego. In this case, ego is set on drawing pleasure from other places, i.e. from without or multiple of the following

1. From superiority over more inferiors
2. From bare minimum, i.e. upto stage 4 and/or stage 5 of journey of ego
3. Hope of eventually elevating to superiority

Along with chase & preservation of superiority forever, stage 7 of journey of ego is also about preservation of superiority-inferiority framework forever.

2.1.3.i | I [identity] in ego is preserved identity | Ego desires forever preserved identity

I in ego, is not the real you, i.e. consciousness, but identity

As we explored just earlier, ego at its core is you. but not the real you. There is a distinction between you in ego, and the real you.

In previous manuscript 'Existence 1', we explored the distinction between consciousness & identity. The identity that we have is the indirect witness of self that we have, as it is the perception that we have of self, it is an analysis of the truth of self-being. Consciousness is about the special aspect of the non-

sensory direct witness. Consciousness is the base for every direct witness of self to exist, as well as every indirect witness of self [identity] to exist.

The distinction between you in ego & the real you is that, you in ego is the indirect witness you have of self, i.e. identity. It is the analysis that you do of who you are.

Your consciousness is the real you.

The real you is beyond the analysis that you do of who you are. No matter what analysis you do of yourself, you remain the same you.

Consciousness is beyond identity.

I in ego is preserved identity

?

In previous manuscript 'Existence 1', we explored the phenomenon of 'the whole you', wrt the phenomenon of identity. Whatever identity you have now, is a variation that got manifested from all the possible variations. Either you can be all of these, or you can be none of these, but you cannot be selective in this, i.e. you cannot be partial in this. So, if you are all of these, then why are you identifying with only one identity, with one set of conditions, and why not any or many other identities with the different set of conditions? And if you are none of these identities, then why do you identify even with your current identity, as you?

Your current form [identity] is a lesser form, and the greater form is who you really are, i.e. the whole you, i.e. your identity as a whole.

So now the question is, are you chasing the whole you, or are you chasing a certain variation of you, a certain set of conditions, which you would identify with, as being you?

Answer

What you are chasing, it cannot be the whole you, especially if you are under the influence of ego. Because, if you accept 'the whole you', the ego dissolves. Only ego-lessness can accept 'the whole you', i.e. the self-identity as a whole. Because the whole you includes superiority as well as inferiority. Accepting the whole you, would make you accept the inherent similarity between everyone, i.e. reject the surface level differences completely. And as we have explored just earlier, comparison & difference are the food (energy source) of ego. Ego desires preserved identity. 'I' in ego is preserved identity.

Ego desires forever preserved identity

As we just explored, ego desires s preserved identity. And as we explored earlier in this manuscript, we want state of pleasure, not peak of pleasure. So whatever identity ego desires, it want to preserve ti forever.

2.1.3.j | Flawlessness of preserved identity related | Ego wants to preserve flawlessness of its identity & everything relevant to its identity

Here is the core reason for desire of ego for having forever preserved identity. As we have explored through previous manuscripts of 'Knowledge sub-series, core of perception is flawlessness, flawlessness of that perception. And as we explored in previous manuscript 'Existence 1', material identity that we have, is the analysis that we make of ourselves in indirect witness. Identity that we have, is our perception that we have of ourselves. And ego desires preserved identity, preserved in alignment with its pleasure. Whatever identity ego has, rather preserves, it draws pleasure from that preserved identity.

But this pleasure that ego draws from preserved identity, its nature is that, it is a peak of pleasure, not state of pleasure.

As we explored earlier through this manuscript, we create an illusion of state of pleasure by having peak of pleasure at our disposable, whenever we want to attain it, multiple times.

Ego wants to keep drawing pleasure by attaining the peak of pleasure multiple times, whenever it wants, to create an illusion of state of pleasure. Ego wants the preserved identity to be available at its disposal, forever.

And this being related to the perception, the core of this preservation is, preservation of the flawlessness of perception which it considers as its identity. Any lack in preservation of this flawlessness, is perceived as flaw.

As we have explored through previous manuscript 'Knowledge 5', meaning is a phenomenon related to alignment of the sub-perception (perception of a phenomenon) with the flawlessness of the perception. Mis-alignment of the sub-perception with the flawlessness, makes that sub-perception a non-sense wrt the relevant perception.

But here, if not preserved, the perception itself becomes flawed, so becomes non-sense. Flawed perception is no perception.

As we just explored, ego wants to keep drawing pleasure by attaining the peak of pleasure multiple times, whenever it wants, to create an illusion of state of pleasure.

Any flaw related to lack of preservation of identity, breaks that illusion. And this crumbles ego.

And here is a thing. Ego wants to preserve not just its identity, but everything relevant to its identity.

2.1.3.k | Journey of ego, stage 2 – 'Desire to be separate from oneness with GOD' | Desire at its core is against GOD | Material world is for desire [ego], by desire [GOD]

Ego at its core, is a desire | Material world exists 'for desire', i.e. 'for ego'

As we explored just earlier, stage 3 of journey of ego, i.e. 'I am', is the starting point of the journey of ego in this materialistic existence, but it is not the real starting point of the journey of ego.

And that is why we named it as stage 3, and not stage 1.

Let us now explore, the stage 2 & stage 1 of journey of ego.

As we explored earlier in this manuscript, desire is the core of our entire functioning. And ego is the core reason for existence of material world. And as we explored in previous manuscript 'Existence 1', the real underlying mechanism of existence is, desire.

So, ego and desire being core to this materialistic existence, then in that case, there has to be some relation, some link between ego and desire. And there is.

Ego at its core, is a desire. Ego itself, is a desire.

As I mentioned in previous manuscript 'Existence 1', material world is for desire, by desire.

'For desire' in this case is, ego. Material world exists is 'for desire', i.e. 'for ego'. The core reason for existence of material world is, ego.

Ego at its core is desire, to be separate

As we just explored, ego at its core is a desire.

Now the question is, what is that desire ?

When you grow up, along with you being identified with your family, you desire to have a separate identity of your own. After you get married, there is a big probability, that you would start considering yourself as a separate family, including your spouse and your kids. So in that case, you would start to act as a separate family, as a separate entity. And if this desire goes to extreme in you, you would even stop relating with other members of your family, as being your family.

As we have explored earlier in this manuscript, difference is the necessity of ego.

We want identity, a different identity; to be specific, a separate identity.

This is a desire to exist as a separate entity.

Even in extended families as well as in friend circle, when ego kicks in, with comparison, competition and power struggles, groups are formed.

When ego clashes happens between two entities, what is the first thing that happens ? Those two entities do not remain being comfortable together. Why does that happen ?

In ego clashes, ego's are heightened, so that desire, which is ego, that desire is heightened. And that desire is, desire to be separate.

Ego at its core is a desire, desire to be separate.

Ego at its core, is desire to be separate from oneness with GOD | Desire at its core is against GOD | Material world is for desire [ego], by desire [GOD]

Our desires has preference levels to them. Desire of the highest preference is the most core desire. That is the core.

And there is more core to ego being desire to be separate.

In general, ego is desire to be separate. But at its very core, what is ego ? Desire to be separate, but separate from what ? What is it that comes at the highest preference for ego ?

Here is the answer. Ego at its core, is a desire to be separate, separate from GOD. Ego at its core, is a desire, to be separate from the oneness with GOD. And this is the stage 2 in the journey of ego.

Ego, at its core, is against GOD. No matter at what point in ego, in the journey of ego, you are, it is against GOD.

Ego IS against GOD. Ego as a complete phenomenon, is against GOD.

No matter what ego based desire it is, it is a part of establishing separateness from GOD. No matter what ego-based desire it is, it is against GOD, against oneness with GOD. Every ego-based desire, is against GOD.

As I mentioned in previous manuscript 'Existence 1', material world is for desire, by desire. 'For desire' in this case is ego.

'By desire', in this case is GOD, i.e. desire of GOD. So material world is for ego, by GOD.

We will explore the desire of GOD, in further manuscript 'Existence 3'.

Note [Against GOD vs betrayal towards GOD]

But note a point here. Even though all ego-based desires are against GOD, not all ego-based desires are betrayal towards GOD. Begin against GOD and betraying GOD, are two different things.

Crossing the line of justice, is, at its core, a betray towards GOD. Desire which does not fit into justice, is betrayal towards GOD.

Ego-based desires which are within the boundaries of justice, even though are against GOD, but are not betrayal towards GOD. Justice is above all & everything.

2.1.3.1 | Journey of ego, stage 1 [start] – 'Journey of ego starts at illusionary belief, of being able to establish pleasurable separateness from GOD'

Ego start with perceiving separateness as pleasure, and oneness as pain | Ego starts at perception

As we just explored, ego is desire to be separate. We desire separate identity for ourselves. As well as, in ego clashes, the desire is to be separate.

But now the question is, what is it that is causing this desire to exist ?

As we have explored earlier in this manuscript, boundaries to desire are drawn by belief [perception], not desire. And we also explored that we cannot choose pain.

So the thing which is causing the desire for separateness is, perceiving the oneness as pain or perceiving separateness as greater pleasure.

It is the perception which causes the ego to exist. Perception is the core of ego. Ego starts at perception.

Journey of ego starts at illusionary belief, of being able to establish pleasurable separateness from GOD

Same applies to the journey of ego.

So here is the most core reason for existence of the phenomenon of ego. At the core of desire to be separate from GOD is, a belief. Belief in a possibility that, it is possible to be separate from the oneness with GOD. Belief in a possibility that, it is possible to establish the separateness from oneness with GOD. And also a belief that, separateness from GOD, from oneness with GOD, is a greater pleasure than the oneness with GOD.

And this is the stage 1 in the journey of ego. This is the starting point in the journey of ego. This is where ego starts. This is where the ego is born.

And the truth of this possibility is that, it is an illusionary possibility, an illusionary idea.

2.1.3.m | Journey of ego, stage 8 – Monstrous goal of ego

We will explore the monstrous goal of ego, further in this manuscript.

2.1.3.n | Overview of journey of ego

Following is the overview of the complete journey of ego

1. Journey of ego starts at illusionary belief, of being able to establish pleasurable separateness from GOD
2. At core, ego is desire to be separate from GOD
3. I am
 - Existing separate (non-absolute separateness) from GOD
4. I am what ?
 - Establishment of separate identity
5. Who else is ?
 - Establishment of difference between our identity & identity of others
 - Forever preserved identity
6. Acceptance from all, forever
 - Establishment of firm grounds for achieving its (ego's) monstrous goal
7. Chase & preservation of superiority, forever | Preservation of superiority-inferiority framework, forever

8. Monstrous goal of ego

This was the overview of the complete journey of ego. But within that journey, we experience ego, as well as we experience ego-lessness which we call as love [desire for oneness]. And this ego-based oneness can also be at some point get under the influence of ego. We can call this as sub-journey of ego.

So this sub-journey of ego also does have the same nature as that of the overall journey of ego. The only difference being, in case of overall journey, the oneness is oneness with GOD, and in general, it is the oneness which exists with others.

2.2 | The philosophical ultimate-closure [circularity] of everything [Direction of ego-lessness]

2.2.1 | The complete picture of phenomenon of desire

2.2.1.a | You have no idea as what phenomenon of desire is

As we have explored earlier in this manuscript, desire is the core of all our functioning. And as we have explored earlier in this manuscript, desire is the real underlying mechanism of existence. Material world is for desire, by desire.

But what these desires really are ? Why do they exist ? Why do we even desire ?

You have no idea as what is the answer to these questions, even though you are living this phenomenon, each & every moment of your life. Even through this phenomenon is inevitable to you.

Desire is a very mysterious thing. But we take this thing for granted, to such an extent that, we completely deny the mystery of desire.

You know that you desire. And to a certain lesser depth, you know what you desire. But you have no idea, as why desires exist ? You have no idea as what really is the phenomenon of desire ?

2.2.1.b | Desire is chase of completeness of self, through oneness | Pleasure is attaining completeness of the desired oneness

?

The first question here is, what is the core of our desire ? In other words, What is the very core of our desires ?

We desire many things, there might be infinite variations to the desire. But the question is, apart from all the variations of desire, what is the base of desire ? What is happening under-the-hood of all the desires ? To be precise, what is the inherent similarity of all the variations of desire ?

You desire completeness | Desire is about going from incompleteness to completeness

So here are some questions.

- When you want something, why do you want that thing ?
- What is that feeling of wanting something ?
- Why do you want to own something ?
- What is this phenomenon ? What happens when you own that thing ?
- When you want to own something, and ultimately you own that thing, why do you feel more pleasure as compared to before ?

Example [car]

Let us take an example here. Suppose that you want to own a car. When you want to own a car, you are basically want to make that car, a part of you, a part of your identity. You identify as being one with the car

And when you want to own a car, not owning that car makes you feel being incomplete. And after you own that car, even through for any shorter period of time or greater, you feel as being complete. You feel pleasure in that, as you have perceived completeness in owning that car, and now you are complete, even though for a certain period.

And this is the core of all the desires. Desire is about chase of completeness. Desire is about going from incompleteness to completeness.

Desire is completeness through oneness

But, what is this feeling of completeness about ?

This feeling of completeness is the feeling of oneness. You desire to be one with whatever that you desire. Whatever you desire to have, you perceive it as oneness which is to be achieved. And you perceive this oneness as completeness. The feeling of completeness is the feeling of oneness.

So you do not perceive completeness on own, but by being one with something else. The completeness you are chasing, is completeness through oneness. Desire is completeness, through oneness.

Pleasure is completeness through desired oneness

When you perceive something as completeness, not having it, is perceived by you as incompleteness. I.e. not having that oneness is perceived by you as incompleteness.

Pleasure is about completeness, & pain is about incompleteness.

Pleasure is attaining completeness of the desired oneness. Pain is incompleteness of un-attained desired oneness.

Desire is chase of completeness of self, through oneness

Whatever you desire, you want to make it a part of you, a part of your identity. And the completeness that you feel, is completeness of you. The incompleteness that you feel, is the incompleteness of you.

So here is what desire really is. Desire is a chase. It is a chase of completeness of self. Desire is a chase of completeness of self, through oneness.

All the actions that you take, all the choices you make, is for the sake of only one thing to chase completeness of self. And you chase completeness through oneness.

Established non fulfillment of desire, feels like a void, because it make you feel being incomplete, incompleteness which would never be able to be complete, through your oneness with it.

Desiring good for others, by making them a part of you

We wish good for our loved ones, why does it happens ?

Because we perceive them as being a part of us. So desiring good for them is desiring good for self. Our completeness exists in oneness with them.

We can classify this situation into 2 types. Following are those 2 types

1. Desiring good for others, based on ego
2. Desiring good for others, based on ego-lessness

Based on ego-lessness

When we perceive our loved ones as being one with us, their incompleteness becomes our incompleteness, i.e. indirect incompleteness. And we desire good for them, from this depth of perception.

This is about desiring good for loved ones, based on ego-lessness.

We will explore more about the phenomenon of ego-lessness, just further in this manuscript.

Based on ego

When we perceive our loved ones as being one with us, we may desire good for them, wrt our perception of good, and not based on their incompleteness. In other words, we desire good for them, which we consider as being good for them, without even asking them as what they really desire. This is about desiring good for loved ones, based on ego. There is ego involved in here, as we are keeping our desire at a higher preference level, than the desire of our loved ones. So the incompleteness is not the incompleteness of the loved ones, but our incompleteness, directly.

Desiring good for others, by not making them a part of you

We can even desire good for others, without perceiving oneness with them. But how is it possible as, if we are not perceiving them as being one with us, then how can we choose to address their incompleteness ?

As we just explored, desire is a chase of completeness of self, through oneness. And in this case, there is neither our incompleteness, nor the perception of oneness. Then what is happening here ?

In this case too, we can classify this situation into 2 types. Following are those 2 types

1. Desiring good for others, based on ego
2. Desiring good for others, based on ego-lessness

Based on ego

When we desire good for others based on ego, even when we do not make them a part of us, then in this case, we are desiring good for others for the sake of our benefit. In this case, even though, on the surface, it might seem that we are desiring good for others, but we are not. In this case, we are desiring good

for ourselves. So in this case, even though the perception of oneness with others is not involved, but the oneness involved here is oneness with the benefit [desired conditions].

Based on ego-lessness, as well as based on ego

When we desire good for others based on ego-lessness, even when we do not make them a part of us, then in this case, the perceived oneness involved is universal oneness. Here, consciously or sub-consciously, you are perceiving yourselves as being one with the existence, so any incompleteness that exists of others, becomes your incompleteness. So you desire good for other, in this case, from this depth of perception. And you are perceiving the others as a part of you, but indirectly. This is about phenomenon of ego-lessness, which we will talk about, just further in this manuscript.

But again, with this perception of universal oneness, you can even desire good for others, based on what you consider should be good for them. This is based on ego.

We had just explored the similar scenario, in the case of oneness [direct oneness] with our loved ones.

2.2.1.c | Ego creates & intensifies incompleteness in direction of ego

Ego creates incompleteness

Example

As we just explored, desire is about going from incompleteness to completeness. Wrt this, let us take an example here.

Suppose that you desire to own a car. So there is incompleteness within you, of not owning a car. And then when you will own a car, it shall be completeness in that aspect, and that completeness shall be a pleasure to you. This phenomenon happens, when, you desire to own a car.

But now the question here is, what if you don't desire to own a car ? Will that incompleteness still exist within you ? The answer is, no.

Then, in the case when you didn't had desire to own a car, in that case, where has that incompleteness gone ? Why did it vanished ?

If you never did desired to own a car, then would that incompleteness had ever been produced within you ? The answer is, no.

So now the question is, the incompleteness which we experience, is it real or illusionary ? Because incompleteness exists in desire, but if you don't desire,

the incompleteness related to that desire does not exist. So is incompleteness real or are we creating it ?

So what is it that is creating that incompleteness ?

The answer is, ego. Ego creates incompleteness.

Ego not just creates incompleteness, but it intensifies it, in the direction of ego

Even if you go for completeness, of the incompleteness that ego creates, do you really feel completeness ? Suppose that, all your desires as of now, are completed in a best way possible, do you really think that you will feel absolutely complete ?

The answer is, no. Your desires will increase to the next level. You will go on to achieve which is perceived by you as higher completeness. In other words, you would chase higher pleasure.

What if even those desires are completed ? Will you still feel absolutely complete ?

The answer is, no. Even if all of the ego-based desires possible are completed, you will not feel absolutely complete. Incompleteness will still persist within you. And it will persist in intensified way.

So here is a thing. Ego not just creates incompleteness, it intensifies incompleteness by creating more and more incompleteness, but in the direction of ego. Ego creates & intensifies incompleteness in the direction of ego.

2.2.1.d | The complete picture of ego-based illusory state of pleasure

Ego elevates your reference of illusory state of pleasure, which eventually becomes pain

Here is a thing. Ego-based pleasure is peak of pleasure, and peak of pleasure is only ego-based pleasure.

When you draw pleasure from ego-based condition, it feels completeness to a certain existence. But completeness is not in the direction of ego, but in the direction of ego-lessness.

Core of ego & peak of pleasure is, comparison.

So peak of pleasure is pleasure, only in comparison. Ego-based pleasure, i.e. peak of pleasure, to feel pleasure, needs comparison.

If you desire to experience peak of pleasure [higher peak than current], and you get to have peak of pleasure, then with that now your reference of what you perceive as pleasure, is elevated. And now whatever is lesser than that, you start perceiving it as pain or lesser pleasure, which [lesser pleasure] itself is pain. So anything lesser than that reference, makes you feel incompleteness. Because you have started drawing pleasure from the elevated reference. Now you cannot stop chasing this elevated reference. Because, as we have explored earlier in this manuscript, you cannot choose pain.

And after you have this elevated reference, at your disposable, i.e. you being able to draw this peak of pleasure, whenever you want, multiple times. With this you create an illusion of state of pleasure.

But now what happens is that, due to comparison being the core, wrt comparison of the elevated peak of pleasure with itself, again & again, the elevated peak of pleasure, no longer remains pleasure. And when the boundaries of desire are broaden, the current elevated reference starts to feel pain, incompleteness.

This is how ego intensifies completeness. Ego elevates this reference of illusionary state of pleasure, more & more, to higher & higher references. And you would realize the intensity of intensified incompleteness, when you try to lower this reference of illusionary state of pleasure.

The reference is not always the illusionary state of pleasure which you chase, but can be some other peak which you perceive as state of pleasure

As we have explored earlier in this manuscript, we cannot choose pain. And we perceive peak of pleasure as pain, so we cannot choose peak of pleasure. We want state of pleasure, not peak of pleasure. But there are times when we do choose some peak of pleasure, knowing that it being peak of pleasure. Then what is happening here ?

You do not perceive any peak of pleasure, as pleasure, then you are not perceiving it as peak of pleasure, but as state of pleasure. And when you chase a peak of pleasure, even with perceiving it as peak of pleasure, you are not really chasing that very peak of pleasure. You are chasing some other reference [of illusionary state of pleasure] which this perceived peak of pleasure is setting at elevated levels. And that elevated

level of the other reference (of illusionary state of pleasure), that is what you really are chasing. You chasing peak of pleasure, is an illusionary idea.

Example

Let us take an example here. Suppose that you have a disease because of which you would be paralyzed for life, after a short period of time. And in that short period of time, you get an offer to be an actor in a big movie. You being an actor, this is a pleasure for you.

But knowing that this would be a peak of pleasure, as you would never act again, why would you choose it ?

Here, though you would enjoy acting, when acting, but knowing that it is a peak of pleasure, you are not really chasing this peak of pleasure. You are chasing the perceived elevated reference that this peak of pleasure is setting. And that reference [of illusionary state of pleasure] is either or both of the following

1. The completeness of desire of acting in a movie
 - So that you would be able to have this peak of peak of pleasure at your disposal, to attain whenever you want, though memory, creating an illusion of state of pleasure
 - In this case, the elevated reference is established in memory
2. The elevated image of you in the perception of everyone
 - In this case, the reference is of the elevated image, not of acting

2.2.1.e | Ultimate truth of phenomenon of desire

Desire & experience are eternal phenomenon | State of pleasure is a phenomenon related to experience

As we have explored in previous manuscript 'Existence 1', the existence in which we exist, is an eternal existence, this is eternity. Everything that exists, exists forever. Your core experience of self remains unchanged, and exists forever, i.e. consciousness exists forever. We also explored that, the answers that we are exploring, scientific as well as philosophical, especially related to the ultimate truth of existence & our existence in it, those answers does not belong to the material world, but to eternity.

Same applies in the case of phenomenon of desires. The ultimate truth of phenomenon of desire is not related to material world, but eternity.

As we will explore in further manuscript 'Existence 3', out of perception & experience, experience is the core of our functioning.

State of pleasure is a phenomenon related to experience. We chase state of pleasure, we chase experience.

State of pleasure is a phenomenon which exists forever. The experience which we are chasing, we want it to exist forever. We cannot choose peak of pleasure, we cannot choose something which does not exist forever [i.e. without end].

State of pleasure is a phenomenon related to eternity. Experience is an eternal phenomenon.

As we will explore in further manuscript 'Existence 3', it is the perception that you have, which would determine as what experience you would have related to relevant conditions.

So experience is beyond the material world conditions.

And this phenomenon remains the same, in real state of pleasure. State of pleasure is beyond the material world conditions, and belongs to eternity.

In previous manuscript 'Existence 1', we also explored that desire is the real underlying mechanism of existence. And functioning does not belong to material world, but to eternity.

Desire is an eternal phenomenon.

Note

Here is a point to note.

As we have explored just earlier in this manuscript, boundaries to desire are drawn by belief [perception], not desire. And it is impossible to reject the aspect [of experience] of highest preference.

So here we are talking about nature of desire when the perception that you have of existence is in alignment with the truth. In other words, when the boundaries to desire drawn by perception, are in alignment with the real boundaries, i.e. includes all the real possibilities & excludes all the illusory possibilities.

And even if the boundaries are mis-aligned, i.e. blocks majority of the real possibilities, even in that case, wrt the aspect of highest preference, you cannot desire something which does not exist forever.

The most common example of the aspect of highest preference is, our image [in minds of others]. We desire to exist forever through image.

Another most common example of the aspect of highest preference is, desire to exist forever. Fear of death is an evidence of it.

So here is a thing. You may have desires only and only related to this materialistic existence, but, understand one thing. No matter what desire it is,

the roots of all and any desire, are not in this materialistic existence. The roots of all the desires, are in eternity.

Desire as a phenomenon, is beyond this materialistic existence. Desire as a phenomenon, has its roots in eternity. Phenomenon of desire, exists in eternity.

Why do desires exist ?

Now the question is, why does the desires exists ?

Indirectly we have already answered this question, through previous explorations of this manuscript.

As we have explored earlier in this manuscript, we desire completeness of self through oneness. And ego creates & intensifies incompleteness. Ego at its core is desire to be separate from GOD.

Desire exists because incompleteness exists. And this incomplete exists because of ego. The incompleteness that exists, is the incompleteness created by ego.

The incompleteness exists because of the existence of separateness from GOD.

And why is the separateness from GOD, an incompleteness ?

Because your completeness of self is in oneness with GOD. Eternal oneness with GOD, is your eternal state of being.

As we have explored earlier in this manuscript, the most core reason for existence of the phenomenon of ego, i.e. for the existence of desire to be separate from GOD is, a belief. Belief in a possibility that, it is possible to be separate from the oneness with GOD. Belief in a possibility that, it is possible to establish the separateness from oneness with GOD. And also a belief that, separateness from GOD, from oneness with GOD, is a greater pleasure than the oneness with GOD.

This incompleteness that exists starts at belief.

What really are we doing in chase of completeness of self ?

As we have explored earlier in this manuscript, desire is the core of our functioning. We cannot do anything without the desire to do that thing. And as we just explored, core of the existence of phenomenon of desire is, the

incomplete that exists due to the existence of separateness from eternal oneness with GOD.

But now the question here is, in our chase of completeness of self, what exactly are we doing under-the-hood of chase of all desires ? In other words, what is the inherent similarity of all the variations of chase that we do of desire ?

Everything that we do to chase our desires, have inherent similarity to it. In other words, all our actions are variations of the same inherent similarity.

You chase happiness, you chase ambition, you study, you play, you watch videos, you eat, you drink, you travel, you talk, you sing, you dance, you have family, you create friends, you do many things.

But no matter what act you are doing to chase your desire, under-the-hood, it is the same act. You cannot do anything else. Doing anything else is not possible, i.e. an illusory idea.

So here is what you are doing, under-the-hood of all the variations of chase that you do in your chase of desire, i.e. in your chase of completeness of self. Whatever you are in eternity, you are trying to achieve that state [state of being], but in this ego state of being, i.e. in the direction of ego. Period ! That's it & that's all that you do, & can possibly do.

The completeness of self that you chase, is the completeness of your eternal self, i.e. your eternal state of being. Whatever ego-based desires you have, in those desires, at its core, no matter what desire it is, you chase to achieve your eternal state of being, i.e. the completeness of your the eternal self.

The experience that you are chasing in the chase of state of pleasure, is the experience that you experience in eternity.

2.2.2 | Phenomenon of ego-lessness related | The GOD mechanism

2.2.2.a | Introducing ego-lessness

As we just explored phenomenon of ego is philosophical theory of everything. And as we have explored in previous manuscript 'Existence 1', material world is a part of eternity.

Phenomenon of ego is philosophical theory of everything, because it is the core cause of existence of material world.

But philosophically, phenomenon of ego is not the only phenomenon. There is one more phenomenon which is beyond ego.

Now the question is, what phenomenon is it ?

Just earlier in this manuscript, we had introduction of the one and only villain, i.e. ego.

And now is the time to introduce the one and only hero. There is no other hero, than this one. It is the only greatness. It is the ultimate beauty. It is the only love. It is the only love of GOD.

And the most beautiful thing that, this hero, can turn even the most negative environment, into the most positive environment for everyone to exist in. This hero can free you of all your pain and miseries. There is no other more powerful force, than this hero.

And the name of that hero, is, EGO-LESSNESS !

As we explored just earlier, ego is a phenomenon which is against GOD.

Ego-lessness is a phenomenon which is in alignment with GOD. Phenomenon of ego-lessness is a phenomenon opposite to the phenomenon of ego.

Ego is a phenomenon which is against the ultimate truth of our existence. Ego-lessness is a phenomenon, which is aligned with the ultimate truth of our existence.

2.2.2.b | Ego-lessness is a complete phenomenon | Ego-lessness is base of functioning of underlying mechanism of existence

Ego-lessness is a complete phenomenon

With the term 'ego-lessness', you might think of it as doing good to others, thinking for others, sacrifice, etc. With this, to some extent you are right, but this could also be a part of the phenomenon of ego. As we have explored earlier in this manuscript, good & evil are to be found in philosophy, not in actions.

So ego & ego-lessness are not the phenomenon related to actions, but intentions [the core desire].

And do not misunderstand ego-lessness, being something as, not reacting at all, not resisting at all, giving up of all the worldly affairs, giving up on worldly involvements, etc. Trying to understand ego-lessness this way, would be a top-down approach of understanding ego-lessness. And with this approach, we cannot claim the understanding of this phenomenon. As we have explored

through previous manuscripts of 'Knowledge sub-series', knowledge is a phenomenon related to bottom-up approach of knowledge exploration.

As we have explored just earlier in this manuscript, ego exists as a complete phenomenon.

It is the same in the case of ego-lessness. Ego-lessness also exists as a complete phenomenon.

Whenever I would be talking about ego-lessness, I would be talking about ego-lessness as a complete phenomenon.

Why would depth of understanding of ego, would reveal everything ? | Ego-lessness is base of functioning of underlying mechanism of existence

As we explored just earlier in this manuscript, when you would understand this one thing to its deepest depth possible, it would reveal everything about the core of functioning of material world.

Now the question is, why would it reveal everything about the core of functioning of material world ?

As we have explored just earlier, phenomenon of ego is the reason for existence of the material world. And as we have explored in previous manuscript 'Existence 1', material world is a part of eternity, and functioning belongs to eternity.

So how is it possible that ego being a phenomenon related to material world, would reveal the functioning which belongs to eternity ?

Deepest depth of the phenomenon of ego is not the deepest depth of our existence.

So when you dive beyond the deepest depth of ego, you still would not have reached the deepest depth of philosophical understanding of our existence. And all you are familiar with is, the phenomenon of ego. So at that point, what is it that you would be into, beyond the deepest depth of ego ?

What is that unknown zone ?

This unknown zone is, phenomenon of ego-lessness.

Diving to the deepest depth of ego, would reveal everything because, it is truly the point where you are introduced to the phenomenon of ego-lessness.

Deepest depth of phenomenon of ego is the point which reveals phenomenon of ego-lessness.

And phenomenon of ego-lessness is philosophical base of functioning of underlying mechanism of existence. Phenomenon of ego-lessness is the base of

functioning of underlying mechanism of existence, as desire is the underlying mechanism of existence.

2.2.2.c | Ego & ego-lessness combined makes the complete philosophical picture of our existence | Eternity is based on ego-lessness

As we have explored in previous manuscript 'Existence 1', the answers that we are exploring, scientific as well as philosophical, does not belong to the material world, but to eternity.

Your philosophical questions remained unanswered, as you were trying to find the answers based merely on the material world & phenomenon of ego. But those answers are in phenomenon of ego-lessness & eternity.

Phenomenon of ego is the phenomenon on which the material world exists, and phenomenon of ego-lessness is the phenomenon on which eternity exists.

Phenomenon of ego & phenomenon of ego-lessness, combined, makes the complete picture of our existence.

So to understand the philosophical complete picture of our existence, we need to understand both these phenomenon to its very depth.

2.2.2.d | Ego-lessness at its core, is a desire | Philosophically, desire is the only phenomenon

Ego-lessness at its core, is a desire | Ego-lessness is desire for oneness with GOD

Ego-lessness is a phenomenon, opposite to the phenomenon of ego.

And as we have explored just earlier in this manuscript, ego at its core is a desire.

So the ego-lessness, at its core, should also be a desire, and it is. Ego-lessness at its core, is a desire.

As we explored just earlier, ego is desire to be separate. And at its core, ego is desire to be separate from GOD.

Ego-lessness is opposite of this. Ego-lessness is desire to be one [oneness]. And at its core, ego-lessness is a desire to be one with GOD, i.e. desire for oneness with GOD.

Philosophically, desire is the only phenomenon

As we just explored, phenomenon of ego & phenomenon of ego-lessness, combined, makes the complete picture of our existence. And both, ego & ego-lessness, at its core, are desire.

Phenomenon of ego & phenomenon of ego-lessness are 2 part of the same phenomenon, phenomenon of desire. So philosophically, there is only one phenomenon, phenomenon of desire.

2.2.2.e | Ego & ego-lessness wrt phenomenon of choice

Ultimately, ego & ego-lessness, are only 2 choices, the only 2 direction, related to the only philosophy [pleasure]

Ego & ego-lessness are about the direction in which we chase our desires. And these are only 2 directions, 2 opposite directions, ego & ego-lessness.

Journey of desire has only 2 direction, one is direction of ego, and the other one is direction of ego-lessness. There is no other direction for chase of desire.

As we have explored earlier in this manuscript, in material world, we cannot escape choice. And the absolute limitation of phenomenon of choice is that, choice can only be in alignment with the ultimate purpose. Ultimate purpose is inevitable. So whatever you are doing, by-default, you are doing it in the direction of the ultimate purpose. It is the perception you have of ultimate purpose, is what is driving your choices. And the only ultimate purpose is, pleasure.

At the core of all the choices that we make, based on the perception that we have of the existence & the ultimate purpose, there are only 2 types of choices.

Following are those 2 types

1. Ego-based choice [Choice in the direction of ego]
2. Ego-lessness based choice [Choice in the direction of ego-lessness]

Ultimately the only philosophy is chase of pleasure, i.e. completeness of self. And there are 2 types of choices that we can make in the chase of pleasure, the ego-based choice or the ego-lessness based choice. These are the only 2 types of choices that exists.

The only 2 types of choices that exists are, ego-based choice & ego-lessness based choice As we have explored in previous manuscript 'Knowledge 4', non-absolute variation is a phenomenon related to choice.

At the ultimate non-absolute variation is the choice between ego & ego-lessness.

Ego & Ego-lessness is about the desire of highest preference

But now the question is, what exactly would determine the type of the choice that we make ?

Your desires have preference levels. And, your desire of the highest preference level, is the only factor which would determine as what type of choices you are making.

As we have explored earlier in this manuscript, ultimate philosophy is inevitable.

Ultimate philosophy is a phenomenon related to the desire of highest preference.

And here is one more thing. The type of choice is determined by your intentions, not action.

As well as, we have explored earlier in this manuscript, good & evil is to be found in philosophy, not in actions. And as we explored just earlier, ego is the only villain. and ego-lessness is the only hero.

Ultimate philosophy is the only philosophy. Ultimate philosophy is a phenomenon related to the desire of highest preference.

Intentions are a phenomenon related to the desire of highest preference.

Ego & ego-lessness cannot co-exist

Here is a thing. On the surface level, it might appear that, sometimes, you are moving in the direction of ego-lessness, and other times, you are moving in the direction of ego. In other words, it might appear that you are moving in both the directions. But, it is not possible.

Because, here the direction in which you are moving, is determined only and only by your desire of the highest preference level, and not by any of the other preference level desires.

And the desire to be separate and the desire to be one, cannot coexist. At core, you are devoted to either to the direction of ego or to the direction of ego-lessness.

Desire of highest preference, can either be ego or ego-lessness. If it is ego, then all your choices are ego-based choices. If it is ego-lessness, then all your choices are ego-lessness based choices.

Ego & ego-lessness cannot co-exist.

Note [Type of choice vs type of action]

Note a point here that, the types of choice that you make, does not define the action that you take based on that choice. Type of choice, indicates merely your intentions. The type of choice & type of action, may be in mis-alignment. Bringing the alignment between the type of choice & type of action, needs knowledge clarity & vision, and not merely the intentions.

You have to inevitably choose the direction | You are already devoted to a certain direction

You have to inevitably choose the direction

As we have explored earlier in this manuscript, ultimate purpose & choice are inevitable. And desire exists because incompleteness exists.

The chase for completeness is on & is inevitable. You cannot escape from choosing either of the direction. You are inevitably moving in either of the 2 directions, ego or ego-lessness.

You are already devoted to a certain direction

You are already devoted to either of the direction, ego or ego-lessness. And it is the desire of the highest preference which would determine as which direction you are devoted towards. Direction of ego & ego-lessness are a phenomenon related to the desire of highest preference.

In other words, all your desires are about chasing completeness in the direction of ego or in the direction of ego-lessness. Even if some of your desires might appear to be mis-aligned with the desire of highest preference, but under-the-hood, they are not.

This devotion to either of the direction, is inevitable, because the chase of completeness of self is inevitable. Whichever direction you are devoted towards, you cannot stop moving in that direction. It is impossible to stop. You cannot stop, you cannot halt, you cannot take break at all. And you never did. Weather you consciously recognize it or not, you are moving non-stop, in either of these two directions.

Direction aligned with ultimate purpose is, ego-lessness

As we have explored just earlier in this manuscript, it is ego which creates & intensifies incompleteness.

Completeness is opposite to the direction of ego. The completeness of self which you are chasing, is in the direction of ego-lessness, i.e. in oneness with GOD. If you are devoted towards the direction of ego, then you are chasing what you want, in the wrong direction.

It is only ego-lessness which is aligned with the ultimate purpose. The completeness of self is in being one with GOD. As it is the eternal truth. Ego-lessness is a phenomenon, which is aligned with the ultimate truth of our existence.

2.2.2.f | Story of ego-lessness related | Phenomenon of ego-lessness is a journey

As we have explored earlier in this manuscript, ego exists as a complete phenomenon, so does ego-lessness.

As the phenomenon of ego is a journey, the phenomenon of ego-lessness is also a journey. Till you have reached either of the destination, you are on the mid-way of the road, which joins both the extremes. The core difference between these two journeys, is the direction in which you are heading.

Earlier in this manuscript, we have explored the story of ego. But, except the destination & brief understanding of the phenomenon of love, we will not explore the story of ego-lessness, in this series of manuscripts. I have kept the story of ego-lessness to be told, beyond this series of manuscript. This series of manuscripts is mere a foundation to the explorations that are coming after this.

Whatever we explored in this series of manuscript, forms the base for story of ego-lessness. Story of ego-lessness is the climax of the story of ego. Story of ego is the story of material world. Story of ego-lessness is the story of eternity. Story of ego is story of use of peak of pleasure for creating an illusion of state of pleasure. Story of ego-lessness is about the real state of pleasure.

And the point to note here is that, this is our story, as ego & ego-lessness are our choices.

2.2.2.g | 2 stages of ultimate destinations in journey of ego-lessness – personal-destination | universal-destination

As we just explored, completeness of self is in the direction of ego-lessness, i.e. in oneness with GOD.

But here is a thing. The ultimate destination of our journey, i.e. the completeness of self which we are chasing, it has 2 stages to it. Following are those 2 stages

1. Pre-ultimate destination – Personal ultimate destination [Phenomenon of moksha]
2. Ultimate destination – Universal ultimate destination [Phenomenon of GOD mechanism | The ultimate mechanism]

2.2.2.h | Pre-ultimate destination – Personal ultimate destination [Phenomenon of moksha]

What is moksha ? | Surrender to GOD

As we explored just earlier, it is only ego-lessness which is in alignment with the ultimate purpose. The completeness of self which we are chasing, is in oneness with GOD.

Moksha is about attaining the ultimate purpose. Moksha is about attaining the completeness, through oneness with GOD.

The core of which is absolute ego-lessness of the soul. The core of which is surrender to GOD, i.e. surrender of ego [desire for separateness from GOD] to GOD.

Wrt phenomenon of form

As we have explored through previous manuscript 'Existence 1', material world is a part of greater form, i.e. eternity. We are a part of the greater form, i.e. eternity. We are eternal being.

Moksha is about merging of our current lesser finiteness, into eternal infiniteness.

Moksha is about merging of our current form, into the greater form, i.e. GOD. Ego state of being is lesser form, ego-lessness state of being is merging with the greater form.

Moksha is the pre-ultimate destination of the journey of ego-lessness. At personal level, moksha is the ultimate destination of ego-lessness.

Working on desire of highest preference | Complete dissolving of ego

Working on desire of highest preference

As we have explored just earlier, ego & ego-lessness are a phenomenon related to desire of the highest preference. And as we have explored just earlier, ego at its core, is desire to be separate from GOD, and ego-lessness at its core, is desire to be one with GOD.

The core desire is desire of the highest preference. For moksha, you need to work on your desires. To be specific, the desire of the highest preference. For moksha, you need to work on the desire of the highest preference.

Complete dissolving of ego

As we have explored just earlier, ego & ego-lessness cannot co-exist.

Moksha is about completely dissolving of ego. And it can be achieved only when the desire of the highest preference is ego-lessness.

In other words, complete dissolving of ego is possible only when your desire of the highest preference is to be in oneness with GOD.

Moksha is primarily a phenomenon related to perception | Moksha is about perception based on absolute logic [established flawlessness]

Moksha is primarily a phenomenon related to perception

As we have explored earlier in this manuscript, boundaries to desire, are drawn by belief [perception], not desire.

So desire of the highest preference is not going to transform from being ego-based to being ego-lessness based, just by desiring it to be so. This can happen only through perception. To make it happen, you need to work on your perception.

Moksha is primarily a phenomenon related to perception. Desires will fall into place, by-default. Because, as we have earlier in this manuscript, we cannot choose pain.

So in the phenomenon of moksha, the target is perception, not desires.

Moksha is about breaking the boundaries of perception that are not aligned with the ultimate truth of our existence. And then re-drawing those boundaries, in alignment with the ultimate truth.

Moksha is about perception based on absolute logic

But here is a thing. Moksha is not about dis-honest faith, dis-honest belief or superstition. Moksha is about honest faith.

We had explored the distinction between these, in previous manuscript 'Knowledge 1'.

As we have explored in previous manuscript 'Knowledge 1', honest faith is a faith based on absolute logic. And in indirect knowing, we cannot claim knowledge, but only faith. It is only for practical purposes that we call honest faith as knowledge.

So moksha is about perception based on absolute logic. As only absolute logic has established flawlessness as its core. A logic without the established flawlessness is a non-logic.

So for chase of moksha, you need to chase absolute logic.

Note – [Use of the term 'Moksha']

Note a point here. The term 'Moksha' is used in certain philosophy(s). I am using it here because of the perception that it holds. Use of the term 'Moksha' here, is not to be associated with any material identity. Knowledge does not belongs to any material identity, it is universal. And associating the term 'Moksha' with any material identity, is a contradiction to the term ['Moksha'] itself.

2.2.2.i | Ultimate destination – Universal ultimate destination [The GOD mechanism | The ultimate mechanism of existence]

Persisting incompleteness | Destination of freedom from ego, is ahead of even moksha

As we have explored earlier in this manuscript, desires exist because of the incompleteness created by ego.

Even if all your ego-based desires are fulfilled, the incompleteness persists.

Even if you bring all your desires to bare minimum possible, even if in that case, you might feel bliss, but the incompleteness, even though with lesser intensity, would still persist.

Incompleteness persists because of the persistence of ego.

As we have explored earlier in this manuscript, peak of pleasure, on its own is futile.

Here is why it is so. After the peak of pleasure is over, you are exposed to the incompleteness that persists. In other words, with the after peak of pleasure is over, the persisting incompleteness reveals itself. With this the illusion of illusionary state of pleasure, is broken.

After the peak of pleasure is over, i.e. not possible even through memory, the existence of that peak of pleasure does not matters anymore. More intensified the ego, more intensified the experience of persisting incompleteness.

But here is one more thing to this. The incompleteness would persist, even after moksha.

This is because, moksha is freedom from ego, at personal level. Ego still persists, even beyond moksha.

Moksha is the pre-ultimate destination of freedom from ego. Ultimate destination is ahead of even moksha.

Dissolving of the ego at personal level, is not going to make us free from ego. Chase of freedom from ego, will still persist.

Intro – The GOD mechanism [the ultimate mechanism]

As we just explored, moksha is not the ultimate destination of freedom from ego.

Now the question here is, why does moksha not make you free from ego ? In that case, how and when shall the freedom from ego be achieved ? What ultimately is the completeness of self ?

The answers to these questions, lie in understanding of the GOD mechanism [the ultimate mechanism of existence].

Earlier in this manuscript, we explored the desire of souls which are in ego-based state of being.

Now is the time to explore the desire of GOD, the mind of GOD.

In previous manuscript 'Knowledge 3', we had made the distinction between, the absolute mechanism & the ultimate mechanism.

When we are talking about the GOD mechanism, we are talking about the ultimate mechanism of existence.

The GOD mechanism is the ultimate mechanism of existence.

With the exploration of the GOD mechanism, we would be exploring the ultimate complete picture, of our existence. Not just this materialistic existence, but also of, our eternal existence.

Base understanding – Phenomenon of love related

To understand the phenomenon of GOD, we need to have a brief necessary understanding of the phenomenon of love.

As we have explored just earlier in this manuscript, ego is desire to be separate, and ego-lessness is desire to be one.

In case of love between multiple souls, the desire to be one exists. And based on this desire, they act as a single entity. This is the existence of ego-lessness between those souls. This is the love between those souls, i.e. dissolving of ego between those souls.

Desires of other, becomes your desires – Phenomenon of love related

When ego dissolves into love of any form, between you & the other soul, you become one with the other. And when you become one with the other, then for you, the other becomes you.

Now that other is no more ‘the other’, it is you, an extension of you. All the aspects of ‘the other’ becomes your aspects. The desires of ‘the other’ becomes your desires, the pain of ‘the other’ becomes your pain, the pleasure of ‘the other’ becomes your pleasure.

One-sided love | Ego-based oneness [Master-slave] – Phenomenon of love related

Now here is a question. What if you love [any form] the other person, but the other person does not love you; in other words, if the ego is dissolved from your side, but is not dissolved from the side of the person that you love ?

In this case, if the ego is dissolved from your side, then for you, the desire of the other person becomes atleast of the same priority as that of your's, if not of the higher priority.

So you would work towards the desire of the other person to be separate. But at the core of it, you would have desire to be one with the other person.

So even though you would work towards separateness, but if that person dissolves the ego from their side, you would accept them as being one with you. And as the love always existed from your side, you were always in the acceptance mode.

Even though you were always in acceptance mode, there is one more factor involved in here. And that factor is, the factor of equality. Ego is a phenomenon related to superiority-inferiority, but ego-lessness, i.e. love, is a phenomenon related to equality. Oneness cannot exist without equality.

Ego-based oneness is based on the master-slave framework.

In which, either of the following can exist.

1. Ego exists from both the sides
 - As we have explored earlier in this manuscript, acceptance of inferiority is also ego
2. Ego dissolved from the side of slave, but not from the side of master
 - In this case, inferiority is not accepted from the slave side, but only for the sake of desires of the master side, slave side is playing the role of a slave

But in either of the case, at its core, separateness exists, not oneness.

Ego wants to own what it desires oneness with.

For oneness of love between souls, ego of all involved souls has to dissolve –
Phenomenon of love related

In love, even if the ego dissolves from your side, but if the ego exists from the side of other soul, then for you the ego still exists. Because 'the other', which is 'you' for you, is still under the influence of ego. So indirectly, you are also under the negative effect of ego.

For love based oneness to be established between multiple souls, ego of all involved souls, has to be dissolved.

The GOD mechanism [The ultimate mechanism] | Mind of GOD

The phenomenon of love which we just explored, is the core of the GOD mechanism [the ultimate mechanism].

The pleasure that you are seeking, the completeness of self which you are chasing, is the state of oneness of existence; the ultimate oneness which is free from ego. This is truly the state of pleasure of existence, the ultimate purpose.

The state of oneness of existence, is oneness of all soul's. Till each and every soul dissolves its ego completely; the true freedom from the ego is not possible for you, for me and for anybody; not even for THE GOD.

GOD cannot get free of ego, unless ego of each and every soul is dissolved. You & no one can get free of ego, unless ego of each and every soul is dissolved.

Ego exists from the side of soul's which exists in ego state of being, i.e. lesser finiteness. Ego does not exist from the side of GOD, but GOD is under the effect of ego.

Your pain is GOD's pain, your pleasure is GOD's pleasure. Your desires are GOD's desires. Same way, your ego is indirectly an ego, an incompleteness for GOD.

Each and every soul's pain is GOD's pain, each and every soul's pleasure, is GOD's pleasure. Each and every soul's desires are GOD's desires. Same way, each and every soul's ego is an ego, an incompleteness for GOD.

Note [Preparing yourself for moksha]

As we explored earlier in this manuscript, moksha is about attaining the ultimate purpose. Moksha is about attaining the completeness, through oneness with GOD. The core of which is absolute ego-lessness of the soul. The core of which is surrender to GOD, i.e. surrender of ego [desire for separateness from GOD] to GOD.

So here is a thing. Preparing yourself for moksha, is about preparing yourself to love GOD. It is about making GOD's desire, your desire.

In state of being aligned with moksha, GOD's desire becomes your desire. Pain & pleasure of all soul's becomes your pain & pleasure.

But as I mentioned just earlier, except the destination & brief understanding of the phenomenon of love, we will not explore the story of ego-lessness, in this series of manuscripts. I have kept the story of ego-lessness to be told, beyond this series of manuscript. This series of manuscripts is mere a foundation to the explorations that are coming after this.

So there is way more depth to understanding the preparing yourself for moksha.

Everything is an expression [manifestation of desire] | Material world is for desire, by desire | Freewill related

The GOD mechanism is why the material world is about desire-manifestation. Truth cannot be changed, and that is why the illusion is manifested for the sake of desire, ego-based desire. Also as we have explored in previous manuscript 'Existence 1', material world is an illusion, also ultimate non-absolute form is an illusion.

As we have explored in previous manuscript 'Knowledge 4', material world is a part of ultimate non-absolute variations. And non-absolute variation is a phenomenon related to choice. And as we have explored in previous manuscript 'Existence 1', in material world, choice is inevitable.

Also, in previous manuscript 'Existence 1', we also explored that desire is the real underlying mechanism of existence. And purpose & action co-exists. Everything about the ultimate non-absolute variation, including the material world, is an expression [manifestation of desire]. Material world exists for expression of the ego-based desire.

Ultimate oneness, i.e. freedom from ego, would also be an expression. The purpose of everything is, expression [manifestation of desire].

Material world is for desire, by desire.

There are two desires involved in here. Following are those 2 desires

1. Desire of souls
2. Desire of GOD

Everything is for desire of souls, by desire of GOD.

State of pleasure | Phenomenon of bliss

State of pleasure is the state of oneness with GOD. Oneness with GOD is the ultimate truth.

The separateness which we are experiencing in this ego state of being, is a non-absolute separateness, an illusionary separateness. As we have also explored in previous manuscript 'Existence 1', ultimate non-absolute variation is an illusionary variation. And material world is an illusion.

State of pleasure is a state, not a peak. In other words, state of pleasure is something which exists forever. And it means that it exists even now.

As we have explored through previous manuscript 'Existence 1', peak of pleasure & pain, exists in comparison. But as per the phenomenon of scope of illusion which we explored in previous manuscript 'Knowledge 3', any phenomenon that we witness based on mere comparison, that phenomenon does exist, but in some other form, not in the form in which we witness it, i.e. based on mere comparison. And the form in which we witness it, is an illusionary form, i.e. an illusion.

The phenomenon which we witness as peak of pleasure & pain, is a phenomenon based on mere comparison. And the way we witness it, is an illusion.

It is a non-absolute form, the absolute core [the absolute form] of which is state of pleasure.

But now the question is, if the state of pleasure exists even now, then how is it that we are not able to experience it ?

The incompleteness is maintained because your ego is not dissolved yet.

As we have explored in previous manuscript 'Existence 1', the absolute core of phenomenon of change is unchanging forever.

The peak of pleasure & pain is a phenomenon related to the phenomenon of change & lesser finiteness [lesser form]. The base on which the phenomenon of peak of pleasure & pain exists, is the state of pleasure, & greater form.

Dissolve ego & the state of pleasure would reveal itself. Your core is state of pleasure.

You already are into completeness. Your core is already completeness.

It is ego that is creating illusionary experience of incompleteness & peak of pleasure & pain.

Even without completely dissolving of your ego, in this ego state of being, it is possible for you to experience, to a lesser or greater extent, the bliss of the state of pleasure which exists as the core of your being. And this is what is the target of meditation.

Here is a brief understanding of the meditation & its target.

As we have explored in previous manuscript 'Existence 1', linearity flow of time is an illusion. The only thing that exists is the eternal moment. And the core experience of self remains unchanged. Through previous manuscript 'Knowledge 3', we had explored that there is a special aspect to our non-sensory direct witness, the aspect which is a direct witness beyond

comparison. And as we explored earlier in this manuscript, conditions affect you as you are drawing pleasure from it.

If you would remove the focus of drawing pleasure, from material conditions, i.e. past & future. And focus only on the present moment, especially the core experience of self, beyond comparison, for drawing pleasure form. That experience itself is a bliss. Experience of this bliss is what is the target of meditation.

Choosing to do so, is possible only through knowledge, clarity & vision. As to choose drawing pleasure from this state, is based on perception.

This state of bliss can be chosen to be sustained. But it would need transformation of perception, in alignment with this bliss. It can be done only with alignment of perception with the eternal truth. And then establishing the transformed perception, in sub-conscious mind.

With this, you would be able to establish yourself into ego-lessness & its bliss, with only bare minimum, strategic & only necessary interaction with the ego-based material world.

2.2.3 | Monstrous goal of ego

Note

Note a point here.

As we have explored earlier in this manuscript, boundaries to desire, are drawn by belief [perception], not desire.

Monstrous goal of ego is a phenomenon related to all the boundaries of desire being open. In other words, when ego is able to believe in its extremes, as being possible.

Ego cannot stop before achieving its monstrous goal, and sustaining it forever

As we have explored through earlier in this manuscript, stopping [the chase of pleasure] before completeness [ultimate completeness], is not possible. In other words, stopping in incompleteness, is not possible. Ego cannot stop, neither can ego-lessness.

Ego cannot stop without achieving its monstrous goal, as it is perceiving that the completeness that it is chasing, exists in its monstrous goal. But it is an illusionary idea.

As we have explored earlier in this manuscript, complete exists in the direction of ego-lessness, in oneness with GOD.

And ego not just want to achieve its monstrous goal, but also wants to make it sustain forever, as it is chasing state of pleasure, not peak of pleasure.

Monstrous goal of ego

As we explored earlier in this manuscript, we chase completeness of self, through oneness. And the ego-based oneness is based on the master-slave framework. Ego want to own what it desires oneness with.

So here is the monstrous goal of ego. Ego ultimately want to own the whole existence. Ego wants to be master of the whole existence, and the whole existence being its slave, including GOD. This is the ultimate superiority that ego is chasing ultimately.

As we have explored earlier in this manuscript, ego at its core is against GOD. Ego, ultimately, is an enemy of GOD, the only enemy that GOD has.

And as the desire of highest preference being ego itself, ego has nothing to do with anything else at all, but to satisfy itself. It can do any evil in chase of its monstrous goal.

As we have explored earlier in this manuscript, ego is the only evil.

And one of the important aspect of the monstrous goal of ego is, to attain ultimate power over all manifestations of material world. The core of this is preserving of the ego-based illusionary state of pleasure.